
Probing Primordial non-Gaussianity due to Axion Inflation using Full Late-time Matter Density PDF.

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Nomenclature and Abbreviation

δ_m	Matter Overdensity
M_{pl}	Reduced Planck mass
$P(k)$	Power Spectrum
ϕ_{NL}	Non-Linear CGF
Ψ	Rate function
ζ	Curvature perturbation
CGF	Cumulant Generating Function
CLASS	Cosmic Linear Anisotropy Solving System
CLT	Central Limit Theorem
CMB	Cosmic Microwave Background
EMT	Energy-momentum Tensor
EOM	Equation of motion
EOS	Equation of state
GUTs	Grand Unified Theories
LDT	Large Deviation Theory
LNG	Late-time non-Gaussianity
LSS	Large-Scale Structure
MGF	Moment Generating Function
PDF	Probability Distribution Function
PNG	Primordial non-Gaussianity
PT	Perturbation theory
QHO	Quantum Harmonic Oscillator

Abstract

Quantum fluctuations in the standard inflationary paradigm are Gaussian in nature to a good approximation. Significant deviation from the Gaussian distribution can occur if there is an interaction between the inflaton field and another field. These are typically called primordial non-Gaussianities. Late-time non-Gaussianity, on the other hand, can arise due to the non-linear effects of gravity during structure formation. The density field distribution then contains information about primordial non-Gaussianity and the late-time non-Gaussianity, and disentangling the two is non-trivial. One of the ways to quantify and analyze the non-Gaussian signatures during structure formation is using the Cumulant Generating Function (CGF) and then computing the cumulants (related to the moments of the distribution) from the late-time non-linear CGF. In this thesis, we build a new framework to study the effect of higher-order cumulants of primordial origin by analyzing their growth after obtaining the late-time non-linear cumulant generating function. We use lattice simulations of inflation to generate the primordial curvature perturbation ζ that contains information about higher-order cumulants. We obtain the linear prediction of over-density δ_m and compute the late-time non-linear CGF from δ_m using the well-established Probability Distribution Function and Path integral formalism. We then subsequently compute the cumulants from it for both Gaussian and non-Gaussian initial distribution. We considered a gauge field coupled to the inflaton in this thesis just as a prototype, but our framework can be generalized to any inflationary model. The overarching goal is to constrain inflationary parameters by analysing the late-time non-Gaussian signatures.

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Inflationary paradigm and Non-Gaussianity

An epoch of accelerated expansion in the early Universe called Inflation was introduced to explain the observed homogeneity and the spatial flatness on large-scales $\sim \mathcal{O}(100)$ Mpc, and the magnetic monopole problem predicted by GUTs [8, 9, 10, 11]. Inflation is a promising paradigm as it also aims to provide a natural mechanism for the formation of cosmic structures during the late-time evolution of the universe. These are formed in a hierarchical fashion when perturbations in the density field cause regions which are overdense to gravitate and coalesce, resulting in a positive feedback loop, wherein the dense regions becoming even denser, and eventually give birth to structures. The origin of these perturbations can be traced back to the inflationary epoch [12, 4]. The interplay between Quantum Mechanics and General Relativity during this era has significant observational consequences and can be experimentally detected, as it results in quantum fluctuations (due to QM) being stretched out beyond the "causal" horizon (due to inflation). These fluctuations remain frozen and become "classical" on superhorizon scales, and they re-enter later imprinting their effects on the background as small anisotropies in the temperature of the Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) and subsequently as seeds for density perturbations [4].

This early accelerated phase of the universe is driven by the inflaton, typically a scalar field. During inflation, the inflaton field "slowly rolls" down a flat potential, and is the source for the expansion with the equation of state $p \approx -\rho$. The scalar field model of inflation predicts that the primordial fluctuations are close to Gaussian in nature, and are nearly scale-invariant [13, 4]. One of the ways to generate significant non-Gaussianity is if there are other fields present during inflation, in general, interaction of the inflaton implies non-Gaussianity. These non-Gaussian features are imprinted on the background due to the constancy of the superhorizon modes, and we can then analyse and compute their effects from the CMB [14] or after the large-scale structure formation (LSS) [15].

Non-Gaussianity, as previously mentioned, is a direct measure of interactions of inflaton and

can be quantified by computing correlation functions. One computes the matter density field correlation function $\langle \delta_m(\mathbf{x}_1)\delta_m(\mathbf{x}_2)\dots\delta_m(\mathbf{x}_n) \rangle$ to quantify late-time non-Gaussianity (LNG) or equivalently, the gauge-invariant curvature perturbation $\langle \zeta(\mathbf{x}_1)\zeta(\mathbf{x}_2)\dots\zeta(\mathbf{x}_n) \rangle$ for primordial non-Gaussianity (PNG). The latter carries information about the inflationary perturbations, and inflaton's interactions. In the standard scalar model inflation, the self-interactions lead to an undetectable amount of non-Gaussianity and, hence, little deviation from Gaussian statistics [1, 16, 17, 18, 19]. This translates to the fact that computing the two-point correlation function or its Fourier transform, the Power spectrum is sufficient to describe the distribution completely. To quantify non-Gaussianity, we invariably need to compute higher order correlation functions, beginning with the three-point correlation function or its Fourier transform, the Bispectrum given by

$$\langle \zeta(\mathbf{k}_1)\zeta(\mathbf{k}_2)\zeta(\mathbf{k}_3) \rangle = (2\pi)^3 \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{k}_1 + \mathbf{k}_2 + \mathbf{k}_3) B_\zeta(k_1, k_2, k_3). \quad (1.1)$$

The bispectrum can further be written in terms of the power spectrum and the ' f_{NL} ' parameter,

$$B_\zeta(k_1, k_2, k_3) = 2f_{NL} [P_\zeta(k_1)P_\zeta(k_1) + \text{cyclic terms}]. \quad (1.2)$$

Planck data constrains the f_{NL} parameter based on the three-point statistics of the CMB, and is $f_{NL} = -0.9 \pm 5.1 (1\sigma)$ [14]. From the large-scale structure end, utilizing the galaxy bispectrum of BOSS DR12 galaxies, [15] constrains $f_{NL} = -30 \pm 29 (1\sigma)$. Detection of primordial non-Gaussian signals is one of the methods to distinguish inflationary models, and constrain model dependent parameters, serving as a window into the earliest known epoch of the universe. It is important to note that detection of a non-zero f_{NL} proves that the initial fluctuations were non-Gaussian, but $f_{NL} = 0$ does not imply or prove Gaussianity [16].

An alternative way to quantify the effect of non-Gaussianity, considering the random nature of quantum fluctuations, is to compute the Probability Distribution function (PDF) of the density field [7, 20, 21]. Utilising a non-perturbative method, we can obtain the full PDF in mildly (quasi) non-linear regimes or focus on the tails of the distribution, i.e. at rare events for highly non-linear regimes [22]. One way the 1-point PDF quantifies non-Gaussianity is via the Cumulant Generating function (CGF) which is obtained after computing the Laplace transform of the PDF. The CGF, when taken derivatives at zero results in connected moments or the cumulants, which just like the moments, encodes information about the distribution. In fact, n^{th} connected part of the cumulant gives more information not contained in the previous cumulant, while additional moments can exist as information redundancy [5]. For instance, for Gaussian distribution, there are just two non-zero cumulants, but higher-order moments can be described in terms of the variance using Wick's theorem. On the other hand, the cumulant of every order in a non-Gaussian distribution sheds new light on the distribution. Both these approaches, correlation functions and PDF/CGF are powerful probes of non-Gaussianity in the large-scale structure, and we focus on the latter in this thesis.

1.2 Inflation and Simulations

Many inflationary models, including the Axion U(1) inflation, which is of interest for this thesis, are characterised by non-linear physics, and invalidates the usual perturbation theoretic analysis [23, 24]. To completely understand and describe the consequences of the model dependent signatures, going beyond the perturbation regime is crucial, and to do that, we turn to numerical simulations.

Numerical simulations are particularly important whenever non-linear effects become prominent. N-body and hydrodynamical simulations for instance, play a crucial role in helping us understand the physics involved during the formation of large-scale structures [25]. Similarly, for this work, we consider lattice simulations to tackle the non-linear evolution and effects during the inflationary epoch [23, 26].

These simulations primarily were designed and being used to simulate, analyse, and understand the preheating and reheating epochs, post-inflation, when the inflaton field decays into the usual standard model particles after rapidly oscillating at its minima [27, 23]. The regime of importance for us is instead during the deep inflationary era, much before the end of inflation, and we use lattice simulations for the same, developed by [24]. We use it to evolve the scalar inflaton field coupled to the U(1) gauge field, and generate the 3D map of the curvature perturbation (ζ).

1.3 From Lattice Simulations to non-Linear CGF

Once we have the ζ map, we "transfer" the map across the radiation dominated era close to the late-time structure formation epoch. This transfer results in the matter overdensity δ_m . Now one can imagine δ_m as a snapshot of the universe at a particular redshift, containing all the information about PNG. The question is as follows: Given this map, how can one determine the effect of PNG once structures form? We then have to perform the analysis that leads to the formation of late-time non-Gaussianity due to gravitational effects, and then disentangle PNG from this. To this end, we follow the spherical collapse formalism, assuming a spherically symmetric configuration with overdense regions gravitating close to each other and eventually "collapse" (virialize). This results in the non-linear density contrast (δ_{NL}) from the initial linear one (δ_L). We then smooth the density field we have, which helps in avoiding large non-linearities and analysing a suitable scale of choice.

From the smoothed field, the non-linear late-time CGF can then be computed via the Laplace transform of the PDF, and then using the path integral formalism and saddle-point approximation to compute the *action* [7]. To elaborate further, since the linear density field is stochastic random, we use a probabilistic approach to determine its evolution. The non-linear density (a functional, dependent on the linear density) is a result of all possible "paths" traversed by the linear density contrast evolution. Hence, we begin by expressing the linear probability density functional in terms of the linear cumulant generating functional, and then we proceed with arriving at the form of the *action*. It was shown in [28] that the spherically symmetric saddle point is a global minimum for Gaussian initial

conditions and can be extended to mildly non-linear regimes as discussed in [7], motivating the spherical collapse approach. The late-time CGF contains information about LNG from the spherical collapse and PNG from the δ_m map.

Once we perform the entire analysis for a Gaussian initial distribution as well, we plot the ratio of cumulants between the non-Gaussian (PNG due to Axion inflation) and Gaussian field (the scalar field inflation). Although there have been recent works on analysing the effect of PNG using late-time matter density PDF [7], this is the first time an attempt is made to compute and analyse the effect of higher order correlators of PNG during the late-time evolution of the universe using CGF approach. To summarise the methodology,

$$\boxed{\zeta(k) \xrightarrow[\text{Inflation}]{\text{Transfer Function}} \delta_m \xrightarrow[\text{Radii } R_L]{\text{Spherical Collapse}} \delta_{NL}[\delta_{L,R_L}^*] \xrightarrow[\text{Late-time}]{} \text{Cumulants}} \quad (1.3)$$

$$\boxed{\delta_{NL}[\delta_{L,R_L}^*] + \text{Linear CGF} \xrightarrow[\text{Saddle Point}]{\text{Path integral}} \text{Non-Linear CGF} \rightarrow \text{Cumulants}} \quad (1.4)$$

The * indicates the saddle point configuration that minimises the action in the path integral formulation, and R_L is the smoothing radii. The detailed procedure and computation is discussed in Chapter 5.

One can further ask, if one does not have the full 3D map of δ_m (translating to having cumulants of all orders), instead had only information about the third cumulant (skewness) or the fourth (kurtosis), will there be any loss of information in quantifying non-Gaussianity? In this thesis, we aim to build a framework to answer this question. We perform the analysis for different initial CGF's, after generating initial distribution with information restricted to only 3-point or 4-point correlation functions, and compare the results of the analysis with information obtained from the full 3D map (\sim n-point correlations).

It is important to note that the framework built is general and can be generalised to any inflationary model, we aim to understand the effect of higher-order cumulants due to primordial non-Gaussianity on large-scale structure using late-time matter density PDF and CGF. U(1)-Axion inflation is a prototype we consider to test the framework. Our methodology and analysis is a novel approach serving as an alternative to N-body simulations to probe PNG signatures during structure formation. In the future, we plan to compare our results with the Quijote simulations [29].

1.4 Thesis in a nutshell

In Chapter 2, we discuss the scalar field inflation and give a brief introduction to U(1) Axion inflation. Chapter 3 is about Lattice simulations, and for a set of particular initial conditions and an U(1) Gauge field coupled inflaton, we discuss the scalar field equations to be numerically solved and obtain the 3D curvature perturbation ζ map. In Chapter 4 we discuss the structure formation and transfer functions and arrive at the δ_m map.

Chapter 5 is about the probability distribution and cumulant generating function in which we discuss methods to disentangle the (PNG) from the usual late-time non-Gaussian effects due to gravity (LNG). We perform the late-time analysis to obtain the non-linear Cumulant generating function (CGF) using the path integral formulation and discuss Large deviation theory in brief. Once we obtain the late-time non-linear CGF, we finally compute the cumulants using a polynomial fitting method. In chapter 6, we conclude and discuss the future work.

Chapter 2

Introduction to Inflation

We present an introduction and motivation to the inflationary paradigm, and discuss the relevant observational constraints for the scalar field model of inflation. A more detailed and pedagogical introduction to the topic can be found in [1, 4, 13, 30].

We then discuss Axion U(1) inflation, its motivation, and cosmological signatures, and we finally discuss the parameters that are of interest to be constrained based on the late-time non-Gaussian effects.

2.1 Motivation

2.1.1 Background: FLRW Spacetime

In general relativity, the spacetime metric $g_{\mu\nu}(x, t)$ is a dynamical degree of freedom that obeys coupled, second order, non-linear Einstein equations,

$$\mathcal{R}_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}g_{\mu\nu}\mathcal{R} = \frac{1}{M_{pl}^2}\mathcal{T}_{\mu\nu}, \quad (2.1)$$

where $M_{pl} \equiv (8\pi G_N)^{-\frac{1}{2}}$ is the reduced Planck mass in the units of $\hbar = c = 1$. On symmetry grounds, assuming that the observable universe is homogeneous and isotropic on large scales, we arrive at the Friedmann-Lemaitre-Robinson-Walker (FLRW) metric. In spherical coordinate system, it is

$$ds^2 = -dt^2 + a^2(t) \left(\frac{dr^2}{1 - Kr^2} + r^2 d\theta^2 + r^2 \sin^2\theta d\phi^2 \right). \quad (2.2)$$

We can imagine our spacetime to be of the form $\mathbf{T} \times \Sigma$, where \mathbf{T} represents the time direction and Σ is a homogeneous and isotropic three-manifold/3D-hypersurface. Homogeneity and isotropy together imply that a space has its maximum possible number of Killing vectors, $\frac{N(N+1)}{2} = 6$: 3 Translation + 3 Rotations for 3D Euclidean space. There is

no time-translational symmetry/timelike Killing vector, the non-existence of such a symmetry demarcates FLRW spacetime from Minkowskian. 'K' in Eq 2.2 is then the spatial curvature of Σ , +1 for positively curved Σ , 0 for flat and -1 for negatively curved Σ . $K = 0$ is observationally supported for our universe, so we shall assume the same throughout this thesis. 'a(t)' is the scale factor and it describes the evolution of spacetime, and since this is dynamical, Lorentz boosts fail to be valid, unlike in the usual Minkowskian spacetime [31].

It is useful (both observationally and theoretically) to introduce the Hubble parameter,

$$H = \frac{\dot{a}}{a} \quad (2.3)$$

The \dot{a} denotes the derivative of 'a' with respect to cosmological time, H^{-1} sets the fundamental time and length ($c=1$ units) scales in the observable universe.

2.1.2 Horizons and Friedmann Equations

Conformal Time

To describe the causally connected regions in our universe, we measure the distance light could have traveled within these regions and extrapolate backwards in time. To measure (note that, measurement clearly illustrates the idea of kinematical horizons, as opposed to the dynamical horizon which is the 4 - curvature scale H^{-1} , a remark we shall return to at a later stage) distances, it is convenient to define the conformal time τ defined as

$$\tau = \int \frac{dt}{a(t)}. \quad (2.4)$$

Then in an isotropic universe, the radial propagation becomes a 2D line element in the $\tau - r$ plane

$$ds^2 = a^2(\tau)[-d\tau^2 + dr^2]. \quad (2.5)$$

Photons travel along null geodesics with $ds^2 = 0$, so the radial null geodesics satisfy

$$r(\tau) = \pm\tau + const. \quad (2.6)$$

Hence, light travels as straight lines along $\pm 45^\circ$ in the $\tau - r$ plane.

Particle Horizon

It is clear from Eq (2.4) that we can measure the distance light travels from t_i to t_f as (in the units $c = 1$)

$$\chi(\tau) = \int_{t_i}^{t_f} \frac{dt}{a(t)}. \quad (2.7)$$

Which we call the comoving particle horizon, (the physical horizon is just $a(t)$ multiplied to the comoving horizon). Since t_i is finite, the distance light has traveled is also finite,

Figure 2.1: Null geodesics and causally disconnected regions shown. The interior of the light cone contains all of null and timelike geodesics marking the boundary of causally connected regions. Credits [1]

hence the causal regions we observe now should "ideally" be within the particle horizon. We further rewrite Eq (2.7) in the following way,

$$\chi(\tau) = \int_{t_i}^{t_f} \frac{dt}{a(t)} = \int_{a_i}^{a_f} (aH)^{-1} d \ln a, \quad (2.8)$$

where $(aH)^{-1}$ is the comoving hubble radius.

Event Horizon

We can also compute the maximum distance traversed by photons if it was emitted at time τ and freely streamed across the universe, in which we alter the limits of integration in Eq (2.7) and we get what is called the event horizon, beyond which an observer will never receive the signal in the future,

$$\chi > \chi_e = \tau_{max} - \tau. \quad (2.9)$$

Friedmann Equations

The Energy Momentum tensor in Eq.(2.1) for observers whose worldlines are tangent to 4-velocity $u^\mu = \frac{dx^\mu}{d\tau}$, and with an assumption of a perfect fluid without anisotropic stresses' contribution is given by

$$\mathcal{T}_\nu^\mu = (\rho + p)u^\mu u_\nu - p\delta_\nu^\mu. \quad (2.10)$$

For an observer in a comoving frame, we have $u^\mu = (1,0,0,0)$ so that

$$\mathcal{T}_\nu^\mu = \text{Diag} (\rho, -p, -p, -p). \quad (2.11)$$

Then using the fact that the EM tensor is covariantly conserved and using FLRW metric to compute the Christoffel symbols, Ricci tensor, and Ricci scalar, we arrive at the Friedmann equations, (after imposing symmetry conditions, as usual)

$$H^2 \equiv \left(\frac{\dot{a}}{a}\right)^2 = \frac{8\pi G}{3} \sum_i \rho_i = \frac{1}{3M_{pl}^2} \sum_i \rho_i, \quad (2.12)$$

$$\dot{H} + H^2 = \left(\frac{\ddot{a}}{a}\right) = -\frac{1}{6M_{pl}^2}(\rho + 3p). \quad (2.13)$$

Combining the above equations (taking the derivative of 2.12 and substituting 2.13, and solving), we arrive at the Continuity equation,

$$\dot{\rho} + 3H(\rho + p) = 0. \quad (2.14)$$

Equating $H = \frac{\dot{a}}{a}$, the above equation shows the dependency of density of different matter components on the expansion of the universe - the scale factor. For matter ($p=0$) $\rho \sim a^{-3}$, for radiation, there is an additional redshift component from its wavelength ($p = \frac{1}{3}\rho$), so $\rho \sim a^{-4}$, and for cosmological constant, $\rho = const$. It is convenient to define the critical density $\rho_c \equiv 3M_{pl}^2 H^2$ parameter such that

$$1 - \Omega_k = \sum_i \frac{\rho_i}{\rho_c}; \quad \Omega_k = -\frac{k}{H^2 a^2}. \quad (2.15)$$

One can also define the fractional matter densities as Ω_i , the above equation then describes the relationship between matter density and spatial curvature.

2.1.3 Horizon Problem

Defining the equation of state $w \equiv \frac{p}{\rho}$ and rewriting the continuity equation as

$$\dot{\rho} + 3\frac{\dot{a}}{a}(1+w)\rho = 0 \implies \rho(t) = \rho_0(t) \left(\frac{a(t)}{a(t_0)}\right)^{-3(1+w)}, \quad (2.16)$$

and for an initial H_0 , we have $(aH)^{-1} = H_0^{-1} a^{\frac{1}{2}(1+3w)}$ (from the first Friedmann equation). If the universe was dominated mostly by matter or radiation, then we see that the comoving hubble radius evolves as either \sqrt{a} or a , and the comoving particle horizon (Eq. 2.8) evolves the same way, hence it increases with time. Note the factor $(1+3w)$, $1+3w < 0$ defines the strong energy condition, the sign of the factor in-turn determines if the comoving hubble radius shrinks or expands. If we trace backwards, we would expect the horizon to be smaller and the regions that we see now which were outside the horizon in the past should not have been in causal contact, but we observe they are! Observations from the CMB shows that it is statistically isotropic and homogeneous, and has regions which are causally disconnected. This implies that they are separated at distances larger than particle horizon

Figure 2.2: Cosmic Microwave Background radiation has inhomogeneity of the order of $\sim 10^{-5}$ K, with the background temperature roughly 2.7 K.

and the inhomogeneity in temperature is of the order of just $\frac{\Delta T}{T} \sim 10^{-5}$ [1]. To illustrate the issue, we can roughly estimate the comoving distance between any two objects from an initial 'a' till now $a_0 = 1$ as

$$\chi(a_i, a_f) = \int_a^{a_0} \frac{da}{a^2 H} = \frac{1}{H_0} \frac{2}{3w+1} (1 - a^{(3w+1)/2}) \implies \chi(a, 1) \sim \frac{4}{3w+1} \frac{1}{H_0}, \quad (2.17)$$

where in the last line, we consider two antipodal objects at the same redshift so χ is multiplied by 2, and we let $a \ll 1$ and other terms are of $\mathcal{O}(1)$. We note that the distance is of the order of hubble radius. We can now compute the comoving particle horizon considering the same condition, extrapolating the radiation era to $a_i \rightarrow 0$

$$\chi(a_i, a) = \frac{1}{aH} \frac{2}{3w+1} \sim \frac{1}{aH} \mathcal{O}(1). \quad (2.18)$$

Note the presence of comoving hubble radius, after dividing Eq. 2.17 and Eq. 2.18 and we see that the ratio is $\gg 1$ in a decelerating universe. Despite this, objects much larger than the particle horizon are observed to have been in causal contact by CMB observations. This is the horizon problem.

2.1.4 Other Motivations: Flatness problem, Phase Coherence, Initial Conditions

Flatness Problem

We revisit Eq (2.15) and we note that since the comoving hubble radius $(aH)^{-1}$ grows with time, $|1 - \Omega_i|$ diverges with time. But now, observations suggest that $k \sim 0$, hence, the divergence is in contradiction with observation, and we need extreme fine-tuning of Ω in the early universe. Why is the universe flat? Matter or radiation domination era in the

past implies that the Ω_k was even smaller. (One more way to see this is to differentiate Eq (2.15) and see that $\dot{\Omega}_k \propto -\ddot{a}$ which in turn is related to $(\rho + 3p) \propto (1 + 3w)$ which is always > 0 .)

Phase Coherence

Cosmological perturbations of all scales, even superhorizon scales ($\lambda > H^{-1}$) seem to oscillate with the same phase in synchrony. This coherence in oscillations is surprising considering the separation scale was beyond the causal region (remember that in a decelerating universe hubble radius and particle horizon are of the same order). How is it that they all are coherent and in synchrony? This motivates the need for a production mechanism that generates all the modes with the same phase and they are then "stretched" to acausal regions. Importantly, since $\dot{\delta} \sim 0$ at the horizon when modes re-enter during radiation dominated era, only the cosine mode of δ is excited [32].

Initial Conditions

Observationally, the CMB is homogeneous and isotropic, but we would expect inhomogeneities to grow with time, a positive feedback loop of perturbations seems natural. But the fact that homogeneity and isotropy is a valid assumption on large scales implies that the initial conditions are to be fine-tuned for an extremely isotropic universe, moreover, this assumption is valid even in superhorizon scales that are known to not have had causal contact with other regions that obey the same symmetric properties.

It is also important to note that the initial hubble velocities are to be fine-tuned to extreme precision for stability. Any lower, the universe would have re-collapsed, and any higher, the universe would have become empty and purely deSitter. This Cauchy initial value problem is to be adjusted so that $\frac{E_k + E_p}{E_k} \leq 10^{-56}$, where E_k, E_p denote kinetic and potential energy respectively of the inflaton, imposing such fine-tuning by hand seems unnatural. [4]

2.2 Inflationary Mechanism

Alan Guth [8] proposed a mechanism to solve the horizon, flatness, monopole problem and it consisted of a scalar field trapped in a false vacuum state at the beginning, and with an equation of state that would drive an accelerated expansion. Later, the false vacuum decays to true vacuum in a quantum bubble nucleation. But this model had a few issues including causality (bubbles get displaced to acausal regions). Later, Linde [11] and Steinhardt and Albrecht [10] introduced what is now called the slow-roll mechanism, in which an inflaton field is in a false vacuum state and it "slowly" rolls during inflation and then decays to true vacuum, and oscillates at the minima to reheat the universe with the usual Standard Model particles [33]. In both the cases, universe underwent an early stage of accelerated expansion that aims to solve the above mentioned problems.

Figure 2.3: Pictorial representation of comoving Hubble radius and comoving particle horizon during inflation and current time. Initially the comoving Hubble radius was large, and it shrank during inflation, and later began to grow, two disconnected regions P and Q were in causal contact in the past but cannot communicate with each other *now*. Credits [2]

2.2.1 Solutions via Inflation

During the inflationary epoch, the comoving Hubble radius shrinks, and this consequently solves the flatness and the horizon problems. Intuitively, the initial modes or perturbations were in causal contact at the beginning (if there was one), and then inflation stretched them outside the comoving Hubble radius,¹ these modes then re-enter at a later time, during the radiation dominated era. We can compute the particle horizon expression during inflation, recall that

$$\chi(\tau) = \int_{a_i}^a (aH)^{-1} d \ln a \quad (2.19)$$

$$\implies \frac{1}{H} \int_{a_i}^a \frac{da}{a^2} \approx -\frac{1}{a_i H}, \quad (2.20)$$

¹This is also called the Hubble horizon in literature, as remarked earlier, this can cause some confusion. The Hubble radius (r_H) is not measurable, hence, it is important to distinguish the conceptual r_H from a measurable particle horizon, the fact that comoving Hubble radius and comoving particle horizon are of the same order does not imply that they both serve the same purpose. H^{-1} is a dynamical 4-curvature scale which establishes a conceptual (as opposed to measurable) boundary of the observable universe. This boundary is important for perturbations and growth of structures since objects within this horizon are in Minkowskian space-time, and hence equivalence principle is valid. The reason this is important during inflation is that inflaton perturbations are the only "objects" during inflation and they cannot communicate beyond this horizon and that translates to causal region/boundary, this is seen in Eq (2.20).

Figure 2.4: The comparison between H^{-1} and the modes (L) during inflation, the latter is stretched with the expansion of the space while H^{-1} is roughly constant during inflation. Once inflation ends, $H^{-1} \sim t$ and $a \sim t^{1/2}$, and hence modes enter the hubble radius. We can equivalently describe this in terms of comoving distances, in that case L would be constant during inflation while $(aH)^{-1}$ would shrink. Credits [3]

for a constant H (approximately valid during inflation) and assumed $a \gg a_i$, so the comoving particle horizon during inflation is of the order of the comoving hubble radius. An initial large $(a_i H)^{-1}$ implies that there was enough time for "light" to communicate to many regions/to travel large regions, establishing causal contact², before inflation. Then during inflation, the comoving hubble radius shrunk translating to a large distance needed for "light" to travel, which translates to acausal regions, hence what we see *now* are these acausal regions which seemingly have been in causal contact, and inflation provides a mechanism to do so (also note that as $a_i \rightarrow 0$, $\tau \rightarrow -\infty$). We can then immediately see that a shrinking comoving radius naturally generates a flat (spatially) universe since $\Omega_i = 1$ is an attractor solution. Also, deSitter (Quasi-deSitter) metric during inflation just like Minkowskian is maximally symmetric and one of the 10 isometries is dilatations $\mathbf{x} \rightarrow \lambda \mathbf{x}$, and $\tau \rightarrow \lambda \tau$, the correlators obey this symmetry and are scale-invariant (approximately) [34].

2.2.2 Conditions for Inflation

Decreasing comoving hubble radius implies $\frac{d(aH)^{-1}}{dt} \propto -\ddot{a} < 0 \implies \ddot{a} > 0$.

We can then define the slow-roll parameter

$$\epsilon = -\frac{\dot{H}}{H^2} < 1, \quad (2.21)$$

²Here by "light" I am aiming to impart meaning to horizons, what I actually mean is the modes knew of each other's existence and homogeneity was established, acausal implies frozen modes.

Figure 2.5: Slow-roll inflation. The inflaton rolls until $V(\phi)$ dominates and the slow-roll conditions are valid, once $\epsilon = 1$, then the kinetic energy dominates and the inflaton field reaches the minima and oscillates, and reheats the universe. Credits: [2]

ϵ determines the end of inflation. We can further solve the Friedmann equation to show that for a flat universe, and violation of SEC, we arrive at $a(t) = e^{Ht}$ during inflation. Acceleration here implies negative pressure, so $p \approx -\rho$.

2.2.3 Physics of Inflation

A simple scalar field called inflaton if made to violate the SEC can be responsible for inflation. Writing down the action non-minimally coupled to gravity as $S_{EH} + S_\phi$, where EH is the Einstein-Hilbert action, we get,

$$S = \int d^4x \sqrt{-g} \left[\frac{M_{pl}^2}{2} \mathcal{R} + \frac{1}{2} g^{\mu\nu} \partial_\mu \phi \partial_\nu \phi - V(\phi) \right], \quad (2.22)$$

Then the EM tensor for the field is

$$\mathcal{T}_{\mu\nu} \equiv -\frac{\delta S_\phi}{\delta g^{\mu\nu}} = \partial_\mu \phi \partial_\nu \phi - g_{\mu\nu} \left(\frac{1}{2} \partial^\rho \phi \partial_\rho \phi + V(\phi) \right), \quad (2.23)$$

And the field EOM is

$$\frac{\delta S_\phi}{\delta \phi} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{-g}} \partial_\mu (\partial_\mu \phi) + \frac{\partial V}{\partial \phi}. \quad (2.24)$$

Now considering the usual homogeneity, and perfect fluid approximation, the energy density and pressure can be expressed in terms of the field ϕ , and in turn we can express the

equation of state. As it is now clear, for $\text{EOS} \sim -1$, we should impose conditions that satisfy such a condition, and we arrive at the slow-roll approximation.

$$\rho_\phi = \frac{1}{2}\dot{\phi}^2 + V(\phi), \quad (2.25)$$

$$p_\phi = \frac{1}{2}\dot{\phi}^2 - V(\phi), \quad (2.26)$$

$$w_\phi = \frac{\frac{1}{2}\dot{\phi}^2 - V(\phi)}{\frac{1}{2}\dot{\phi}^2 + V(\phi)}. \quad (2.27)$$

If the potential energy dominates over kinetic for the most part of inflation, then $w_\phi \sim -1$. The dynamics of the scalar field is then determined by the following equations (using continuity equation and substituting in the above, we get a Klein-Gordon Equation for the scalar field),

$$\ddot{\phi} + 3H\dot{\phi} + \frac{\partial V}{\partial \phi} = 0, \quad (2.28)$$

$$H^2 = \frac{1}{3} \left[\frac{1}{2}\dot{\phi}^2 + V(\phi) \right]. \quad (2.29)$$

The above equations make the conditions for slow-roll clearer. Along with ϵ , we also need a condition that $|\ddot{\phi}| \ll |3H\dot{\phi}|, |\frac{\partial V}{\partial \phi}|$, from this we get the second slow-roll parameter $\eta = \epsilon - \frac{d \ln \epsilon}{2H dt} = -\frac{\ddot{\phi}}{\dot{\phi}H}$, hence $|\eta| < 1$. This parameter decides the rate of variation of ϵ , and that should be small. Two things to note: the velocity of the inflaton is minimal during most of the inflationary epoch; and we notice from Eq. 2.29 that if the velocity is subdominant, the Hubble parameter depends only on the potential which implies that it too is roughly a constant, as expected. We can finally introduce the number of e-folds, given by $N_e = \ln \frac{a_f}{a} = \int_{t_i}^t H dt = \frac{\phi_f}{\phi} \frac{H}{\dot{\phi}} d\phi$, and to solve all the Big Bang problems, we need at least 60 e-folds, CMB scales leave the horizon roughly 55 e-folds before the end of inflation.

2.3 Quantum Fluctuations and The Inhomogeneous Universe

The next question that arises is if inflation is responsible for a homogeneous and an isotropic universe, how is it that structures form? Why is the CMB with temperature anisotropies of the order of 10^{-5} ? We then inevitably deviate from classical description to a quantum mechanical one, and rely on the Heisenberg uncertainty principle. Quantum mechanical description implies fluctuations in the background. When the inflaton rolls down the potential, quantum fluctuations continuously form and they are stretched to superhorizon scales where they become "classical", and $\hbar \rightarrow 0$ approximation is valid. These fluctuations cause a local time delay and different parts inflate a bit more than the rest. This induces enhanced $\delta\phi$ in some parts and that subsequently leads to different δT and $\delta\rho$. To quantify

Figure 2.6: Quantum Fluctuations are continuously created during inflation and they are stretched to superhorizon scales with amplitude $\Delta\phi_{\text{quantum}} \sim H$. Credits: [4]

the effect of these fluctuations classically, we perturb the relevant parameters and solve the Einstein's equations at the linear order of perturbations.

2.3.1 Cosmological Perturbations

We begin by splitting the inflaton field into the time-dependent homogeneous background and the perturbed part which varies with both space and time.

$$\phi(\mathbf{x}, t) = \bar{\phi}(t) + \delta\phi(\mathbf{x}, t). \quad (2.30)$$

We then further proceed to perturb the metric and compute the usual Ricci tensors, Ricci scalar and other parameters, but a crucial aspect to keep in mind is about the gauge choice. The background and the perturbation live on different space-time, and the gauge choice maps the points between the two different space-times. It is evidently not unique since we can slice space and time in multiple equivalent ways. The freedom leads to arbitrariness in the value of the perturbed parameter unless it is gauge-invariant. To distinguish fictitious perturbations from real ones, we compute both the metric and the matter field perturbations and include the gauge choice to map between them.

A homogeneous and isotropic background results in a convenient set of decomposition of the metric into Scalar, Vector, and Tensor (SVT) variables. They evolve independently in the first order due to rotational invariance and can be decomposed into Fourier modes [1]. For example, consider rotations of the variable $X \rightarrow e^{im\theta} X$, where m is the helicity which is 0 for scalar, ± 1 for vector and ± 2 for tensor. We now decompose the metric into the background and the perturbation part and write down each component of SVT. This relies on splitting a vector into two parts: a divergence-free vector and gradient of a scalar, and generalising this formalism to tensors (Helmholtz theorem generalisation known as Hodge decomposition, this lets us write a vector as two modes - a scalar mode and a div-free

vector mode, and we can use further constraints to arrive at 10 components, in-line with 10 DOF of the symmetric metric tensor).

$$g_{\mu\nu}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \bar{g}_{\mu\nu}(t) + \delta g_{\mu\nu}(\mathbf{x}, t), \quad (2.31)$$

$$ds^2 \equiv g_{\mu\nu} dx^\mu dx^\nu, \quad (2.32)$$

$$= -(1 + 2\Phi)dt^2 + 2aB_i dx^i dt + a^2(t)[(1 - 2\Psi)\delta_{ij} + E_{ij}]dx^i dx^j, \quad (2.33)$$

where

$$B_i \equiv \partial_i B - J_i; \quad \partial^i J_i = 0, \quad (2.34)$$

$$E_{ij} \equiv 2\partial_{ij} E + 2\partial_{(i} F_{j)} + h_{ij}; \quad \partial^i F_i = 0; \quad h_{ii}, \partial^i h_{ij} = 0, \quad (2.35)$$

J_i, F_i are vector perturbations that decay with the expansion and are not important³. Tensor perturbations are gauge invariant, and this is manifest in the matter perturbations, as the anisotropic stress tensor is gauge-invariant. It is then important to determine the gauge invariant variables for scalar perturbations as well. One of them is the curvature perturbation on uniform density hypersurfaces defined as

$$-\zeta \equiv \Psi + \frac{H}{\dot{\rho}} \delta\rho, \quad (2.36)$$

ζ measures the spatial curvature on uniform density hypersurfaces where the spatial part of the Ricci tensor is $R^{(3)} = 4\frac{\nabla^2 \Psi}{a^2}$. For adiabatic matter perturbations, ζ is constant on superhorizon scales, owing to locally conserved EM Tensor [35]. During slow roll $-\zeta \equiv \Psi + \frac{H}{\dot{\phi}} \delta\phi$.⁴ Equivalently, we can define the comoving curvature perturbation as

$$\mathcal{R} \equiv \Psi - \frac{H}{\bar{\rho} + \bar{p}} \delta q, \quad (2.37)$$

δq is the scalar part of the 3-momentum density and both \mathcal{R} and ζ are approximately equal on superhorizon scales (their difference depends on $(\frac{k}{aH})^2$ which is suppressed for $k \ll aH$) [13, 36]. This can be intuitively seen as follows: On the superhorizon scales, perturbations cannot "communicate", hence we can use the uniform density gauge to compute cosmological parameters by setting $\delta\rho = 0$. On the same scales, we can also use comoving gauge by setting the 3-momentum density to be zero, hence $\mathcal{R} \sim -\zeta$. (In case of subhorizon scale, one utilises the spatially flat gauge by setting $\Psi = E = 0$, approaching the Newtonian limit.)

Assuming adiabatic matter perturbations on superhorizon scales, we shall use ζ throughout this thesis even if we mean \mathcal{R} at times.

³Supposedly, except primordial magnetic fields

⁴"Adiabatic" means that the total density of the Universe may vary from one region to another, but the ratio of various components e.g., the photon-to-baryon ratio is the same everywhere. The perturbation $\delta\phi(t, \mathbf{x}) = \dot{\phi}\delta t(\mathbf{x})$ leads to a local time delay in the background solution, as mentioned before. This after reheating posits a condition on the ratio of the different component densities for $\delta S = 0$. Isocurvature perturbations on the other hand change the relative density but not the total density, in turn they are not isentropic.

2.3.2 Statistics and Perturbations

Quantum fluctuations are inherently random in nature, hence if these fluctuations are responsible for cosmological perturbations, assuming it to be statistically random is a valid assumption. We can then define a Gaussian random field since any set of 'N' random fields if they are identically distributed and independent (i.i.d), will converge to a Gaussian random field for $N \rightarrow \infty$ due to the Central Limit Theorem (CLT). If the quantum fluctuations are Gaussian random, then the curvature perturbation ζ describes the field with just the amplitude of its 2-point correlation function as mentioned in Chapter 1,

$$\langle \zeta_{\mathbf{k}} \zeta_{\mathbf{k}'} \rangle = (2\pi)^3 \delta(\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}') P_{\zeta}(k); \quad \Delta_{\zeta}^2 = \frac{k^3}{2\pi^2} P_{\zeta}(k). \quad (2.38)$$

The scale dependence of the power spectrum is given by

$$n_s - 1 = \frac{d \ln \Delta_{\zeta}^2}{d \ln k}, \quad (2.39)$$

and the running $\alpha_s = \frac{d \ln n_s}{d \ln k}$.⁵ This parameter can be constrained using the power spectrum measured from the CMB data. The result from the Planck satellite is: $n_s = 0.9649 \pm 0.0044$ at 68% confidence level [37, 13]. This is compatible with slow-roll inflation, which predicts a small deviation from $n_s = 1$ as a consequence of the quasi-de Sitter dynamics. Fourier transforming the correlation function leads to the variance of the field, which in turn is related to the power spectrum. The variance alone completely describes a Gaussian field, and higher order correlators can be written in terms of the variance by the Wick's theorem.

Inducing a variance in the field is closely related to the variance in zero-point fluctuations in the ground state of a free field Quantum Harmonic Oscillator (QHO) [38]. Inflationary perturbations can be quantized and modeled as QHO owing to the simple fact that most potentials can be approximated to that of a QHO. Remember that the ground state of QHO in the $\phi(\mathbf{k})$ representation is of the form of a Gaussian wavepacket.

Quantization

To quantize inflationary perturbations, we first define the action as

$$S = \frac{1}{2} \int d^4x \sqrt{-g} [R - (\nabla\phi)^2 - m^2\phi^2], \quad (2.40)$$

where we work in the units $M_{pl} \equiv 1$, we can also work with arbitrary potentials. We then fix

$$\delta\phi = 0; \quad g_{ij} = a^2[(1 - 2\zeta)\delta_{ij} + h_{ij}]. \quad (2.41)$$

⁵The power spectrum varying as $\frac{1}{k^3}$ can also be seen considering the dilatation symmetry of the deSitter space [31].

In this gauge the inflaton perturbation is zero and the perturbation solely is contained in the metric, and after writing the above equation in second order in ζ , we get (for detailed calculations, see [13]),

$$S = \frac{1}{2} \int d^4x a^3 \frac{\dot{\phi}^2}{H^2} \left[\dot{\zeta}^2 - \frac{(\partial_i \zeta)^2}{a^2} \right]. \quad (2.42)$$

We can then define the Mukhanov variable $z \equiv v\zeta$, where $z \equiv a^2 \frac{\dot{\phi}^2}{H^2}$, and in conformal time we have,

$$S = \frac{1}{2} \int d\tau d^3x \left[(v')^2 + (\partial_i v)^2 + \frac{z''}{z} v^2 \right], \quad (2.43)$$

and in Fourier space,

$$v_k'' + \left(k^2 - \frac{z''}{z} \right) v_k = 0. \quad (2.44)$$

We now promote v to an operator and quantize it, further, imposing the vacuum conditions, we arrive at the final form of the mode function,

$$\hat{v}_{\mathbf{k}} = \int \frac{d^3\mathbf{k}'}{(2\pi)^3} \left[\hat{v}_k(\tau) \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}} e^{i\mathbf{k}\mathbf{x}} + \hat{v}_k^*(\tau) \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger e^{-i\mathbf{k}\mathbf{x}} \right]. \quad (2.45)$$

Following the usual QFT approach, we can then impose the commutation relations for the ladder operators $[\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}, \hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}'}^\dagger] = (2\pi)^3 \delta(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}')$, only if the mode function is normalised $\langle v_k v_k \rangle = 1$.

After fixing the Bunch-Davies vacuum condition $\hat{a}_{\mathbf{k}}|0\rangle = |0\rangle$, and imposing the initial condition for all the modes within the comoving hubble radius $k \gg aH$, as $\tau \rightarrow -\infty$, we arrive at (this just implies all the modes are in the Minkowskian background, they can't 'see' the curvature),

$$v_k'' + k^2 v_k = 0 \quad (2.46)$$

$$\lim_{\tau \rightarrow -\infty} v_k = \frac{e^{-ik\tau}}{\sqrt{2k}}. \quad (2.47)$$

Now, in the deSitter limit of a constant 'H', we can fix the initial condition by the above considerations (we solve Eq 2.44 for $\frac{z''}{z} = \frac{a''}{a}$),

$$v_k = \frac{e^{-ik\tau}}{\sqrt{2k}} \left(1 - \frac{i}{k\tau} \right). \quad (2.48)$$

Computing the power spectrum is trivial since the variance $|v_k(\tau)|^2$ is now known. Of course, we can change the gauge and obtain the same result for spatially flat gauge with $\Psi = 0$ and considering $\delta\phi$. Then, we will arrive at $\zeta \approx -H \frac{\delta\phi}{\dot{\phi}}$.

Finally, deviations from the potential of the inflaton or coupling the scalar field to other fields implying interactions, can lead to non-Gaussian features. In that case, the QHO framework needs to be modified to consider the source terms, and we need additional analysis to understand the cosmological signatures, while keeping the observational constraints

fixed and within bounds. Hence, to probe non-Gaussianity which is insignificant in the single field inflaton, we are forced to consider interactions with other fields which we shall do next. ⁶

2.4 Axion Inflation

We begin with a primer to Effective Field Theory and its relevance in understanding Inflation. This would then naturally motivate Axion/Axion-like inflationary models.

2.4.1 EFT and the η Problem

We first write down the Lagrangian considering symmetries and including the higher order operators during inflation,

$$\mathcal{L} = \sum_i \frac{\mathcal{O}_i}{\Lambda^{D_i-4}} = \frac{1}{2}(\partial_\mu\phi)^2 - V(\phi) + \sum_n c_n V(\phi) \frac{\phi^{2n}}{\Lambda^{2n}} + \sum_n d_n \frac{(\partial\phi)^{2n}}{\Lambda^{4n}}. \quad (2.49)$$

During Inflation, even Planck-suppressed operators do not decouple and their effects are important, for details see [1, 40].

The second slow-roll condition, $\eta = -\frac{\ddot{\phi}}{\dot{\phi}H} = \frac{m_\phi^2}{3H^2} \ll 1$ is sensitive to higher-order corrections. Increasing the energy scale to the scale of either string theory or any theory of quantum gravity that has a cutoff M such that $\Lambda \leq M \leq M_{pl}$, and if the inflaton couples to a massive field $\psi \sim \Lambda$, then integrating out the massive field can give rise to correction to the potential of the form $\Delta V = c_1 V(\phi) \frac{\phi^2}{\Lambda^2}$, (first order correction from Eq. 2.49). This would in turn affect the η parameter as $\Delta\eta = M_{pl}^2 \frac{\Delta V''}{V}$, of the order of $\left(\frac{M_{pl}}{\Lambda}\right)^2$ and since $M_{pl} \geq \Lambda$, $\Delta\eta \geq 1$, this affects the slow-roll background. Moreover, ratio of *height* to (*width*)⁴ of the potential is of the order $\frac{\Delta V}{(\Delta\phi)^4} \sim 10^{-6} - 10^{-8}$, for the required number of e-folds [41].

So, for the above issue and to protect from higher order corrections contribution, we can impose an additional symmetry on the inflaton: $\phi = \phi + c$, the so-called shift symmetry. We can further consider the inflaton to be a Pseudo-Nambu-Goldstone-Boson (PNGB) with a shift symmetry and the symmetry is broken non-perturbatively (instantons) ⁷. It is by definition a pseudo-scalar and ($\phi(-\vec{x}) = -\phi(\vec{x})$). The inflaton becomes a Goldstone boson when the symmetry is exact, hence such approximately broken symmetry induces a small mass protecting it from UV corrections [42]. The first model of this kind was discussed

⁶Creminelli and Zaldarriaga [39] proved that $\lim_{k_1 \rightarrow 0} \langle \zeta_{\mathbf{k}_1} \zeta_{\mathbf{k}_2} \zeta_{\mathbf{k}_3} \rangle = (2\pi)^3 (1 - n_s) P_\zeta(k_1) P_\zeta(k_2) \delta(\mathbf{k}_1 + \mathbf{k}_2 + \mathbf{k}_3)$ in the squeezed limit for single-field inflation, hence for a nearly scale invariant spectrum, non-Gaussianity is negligible and cannot be detected, both CLT and this provides a way to understand the Gaussian distribution.

⁷A PNGB is produced whenever the symmetry of the potential is different from the symmetry of the Lagrangian. The kinetic term obeys shift symmetry but the potential breaks it, explicitly.

[41] called Natural Inflation considered a periodic potential of the form

$$V(\phi) = \Lambda^4 \left[1 - \cos \left(\frac{\phi}{f} \right) \right], \quad (2.50)$$

breaking the symmetry down to discrete subgroup $\phi \rightarrow \phi + 2\pi f$. (Λ is the scale of its explicit breaking and f is the Spontaneous breaking scale.) It was motivated by the QCD Axion, and in that case for temperatures (energy scale) $T \leq f$, the global symmetry is spontaneously broken, and the field ϕ drops to the minima of the usual "mexican-hat" potential. It thermally decouples at temperature $T \sim \frac{f^2}{M_{pl}} \sim f$. Unfortunately, this model is observationally compatible only if $f > M_{pl}$ [43] which is not possible to be systematically realized in the EFT framework (decoupling temperature is beyond M_{pl} , hence, as previously mentioned, corrections to the potential is inevitable) [44]. If we consider the U(1) Axion inflation, the model of interest, we then have the interaction Lagrangian of the type,

$$\mathcal{L}_{int} = -\frac{\alpha}{4f} \phi F_{\mu\nu} \tilde{F}^{\mu\nu}. \quad (2.51)$$

If ϕ is a pseudo-scalar, then effective field theory *requires* that the interaction Lagrangian is of the above form, $F_{\mu\nu}$ is the EM tensor of the gauge field and \tilde{F} is its Hodge dual [44]. This type of coupling does not circumvent the $f > M_{pl}$ problem, there are models that aim to tackle this issue with more than one axion field [45], or N-axions [46]. But, any Axion model should have a coupling of the form in Eq. 2.51, and they have certain cosmological signatures, for example, the coupling provides a natural decay channel for the axion to produce gauge bosons during reheating [47]. In this thesis we do not delve into the details of a particular model, and as mentioned, the framework we are working on is general and it is just a phenomenological study of U(1)-Axion Inflation, considering non-Gaussianity as the signature.

2.4.2 The Model

We begin with considering the Lagrangian of the form

$$S = \int d^4x \sqrt{-g} \left[\frac{M_{pl}^2}{2} \mathcal{R} - \frac{1}{2} (\partial_\mu \phi)^2 - V(\phi) - \frac{1}{4} F^{\mu\nu} F_{\mu\nu} - \frac{\alpha}{4f} \phi F^{\mu\nu} \tilde{F}_{\mu\nu} \right], \quad (2.52)$$

where \mathcal{R} is the Ricci Scalar, $F_{\mu\nu} = \partial_\mu A_\nu - \partial_\nu A_\mu$ is the field strength, and $\tilde{F}^{\mu\nu} \equiv \frac{\epsilon^{\mu\nu\rho\sigma}}{2F_{\rho\sigma}}$, $\epsilon^{0123} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{-g}}$. We remind the reader that working in the reduced Planck units $M_{pl} = 1$. Due to the motion of the inflaton, there is an exponential production (tachyonic) of a gauge field of one helicity more than the other, and this has observational consequences. To describe this production, consider the unperturbed FLRW metric in conformal time,

$$ds^2 = a^2(\tau) [-d\tau^2 + d\mathbf{x}^2]. \quad (2.53)$$

We split the inflaton field into the background and perturbed part, and set $\langle A_\mu \rangle = 0$, considering only perturbations to the gauge field $A_\mu = \delta A_\mu$, and set $\delta g_{\mu\nu} = 0$, considering only the background contribution to the metric. We begin with quantizing the gauge field

$$\vec{A}(\tau, \vec{x}) = \sum_{\lambda=\pm} \int \frac{d^3\mathbf{k}}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} \left[\vec{\epsilon}_\lambda(\vec{k}) \vec{A}_\lambda(\tau, \vec{k}) \hat{a}_{\vec{k}} e^{-i\mathbf{k}x} \right] + h.c. \quad (2.54)$$

The creation annihilation operator and the polarization vectors satisfy,

$$[\hat{a}_{\vec{k}}, \hat{a}_{\vec{k}'}^\dagger] = \delta(\vec{k} - \vec{k}'), \quad (2.55)$$

$$\epsilon_\lambda^*(\vec{k}) \epsilon_{\lambda'}(\vec{k}) = \delta_{\lambda\lambda'}; \quad \vec{k} \epsilon_\pm(\vec{k}) = 0; \quad \vec{k} \times \vec{\epsilon}_\pm(\vec{k}) = \mp i k \vec{\epsilon}_\pm(\vec{k}). \quad (2.56)$$

Plugging the above in the action and neglecting metric contribution to perturbations results in

$$A_\pm'' + \left(k^2 \pm k \bar{\phi}' \frac{\alpha}{f} \right) A_\pm = 0 \quad (2.57)$$

If the gauge field coupling was absent, $\frac{\alpha}{f} = 0$ and the field just oscillates. But the presence of the coupling term indicates a tachyonic growth of a gauge field of one of the two polarizations for $k < \bar{\phi}' \frac{\alpha}{f}$. For $\bar{\phi}' > 0$, which we can freely choose, we then get A_- as the growing gauge field. We can further introduce

$$\xi = \frac{\alpha \dot{\phi}}{2fH}. \quad (2.58)$$

So modes $k < 2\xi aH$ are excited, and we can determine the form of the gauge field and its dependency on ξ as follows, following [24, 44],

$$A_\pm(\vec{k}, \tau) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2k}} e^{-i\omega_k \tau}; \quad -k\tau \gg 1; \quad -k \bar{\phi}' \frac{\alpha}{f} = 2 \frac{\xi}{\tau}, \quad (2.59)$$

$$A_-(k, \tau) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2k}} [G_0(\xi, -k\tau) + iF_0(\xi, -k\tau)], \quad (2.60)$$

where F_0, G_0 are the Coulomb wave functions. In Eq. 2.59 we assumed a Bunch-Davies vacuum condition. The production of the gauge quanta is maximum for $-k\tau \ll 1$, and $e^{\pi\xi} \gg 1$, we can approximate Eq 2.60 in terms of modified Bessel function, and arrive at

$$A_-(k, \tau) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2k}} \left(-\frac{k\tau}{2\xi} \right) e^{(\pi\xi - 2\sqrt{-2\xi k\tau})}; \quad (8\xi)^{-1} \leq \frac{k}{aH} \leq 2\xi, \quad (2.61)$$

this sets the domain of validity of the exponential production of the gauge field in terms of the modes of interest. We observe the exponential dependency on ξ by the growing gauge field, and this has significant consequences on both the scalar and tensor perturbations, and we focus on the former in this thesis.

2.4.3 Cosmological Signatures: Scalar Perturbations and Non-Gaussianity

The exponential production of the field sources the scalar perturbations via the inverse decay process, the rolling inflaton sources the gauge field which in-turn sources scalar perturbations, $\delta A + \delta A \rightarrow \delta\phi$, and this is maximum when $(8\xi)^{-1} \leq \frac{k}{aH} \leq 2\xi$ and for $\frac{f}{\alpha} \leq 10^{-2}M_{pl}$. This new source of perturbations dominates over the perturbations from the vacuum/free field ⁸.

The scalar perturbations are of the form

$$\left(\frac{\partial^2}{\partial\tau^2} + 2\mathcal{H}\frac{\partial}{\partial\tau} - \nabla^2 + a^2m^2\right)\delta\phi(\vec{x},\tau) = a^2\frac{\alpha}{f}\left(F_{\mu\nu}\tilde{F}^{\mu\nu} - \langle F_{\mu\nu}\tilde{F}^{\mu\nu}\rangle\right). \quad (2.62)$$

The perturbations can further be divided into the vacuum contributions and source contribution, accordingly, we can decompose $\delta\phi$ as

$$\delta\phi_{\mathbf{k}}(\tau, \mathbf{x}) = \int \frac{d^3k}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} \frac{Q_{\mathbf{k}}}{a(\tau)} e^{i\mathbf{k}\mathbf{x}}, \quad (2.63)$$

substituting this back in 2.62 gives two different equations, one the homogeneous solution of the vacuum, the other, with the source which we are interested in,

$$\left[\frac{\partial^2}{\partial\tau^2} + k^2 + a^2m^2 - \frac{a''}{a}\right] Q_{\mathbf{k}}^s(\tau) = J_{\mathbf{k}}(\tau), \quad (2.64)$$

$$J_{\mathbf{k}}(\tau) = a^3(\tau)\frac{\alpha}{f} \int \frac{d^3\mathbf{k}}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} e^{-i\mathbf{k}\mathbf{x}} \vec{E} \cdot \vec{B}. \quad (2.65)$$

We can then separate the mode function $Q_{\mathbf{k}}$ as sum of vacuum and source terms, and the ladder operators commute with each other. From there we can compute the form of correlation functions, ($Q_k(\tau) \sim \int d\tau' G(\tau, \tau') J_k(\tau')$), the two-point correlation function can also be written as a sum of the vacuum and the source, and they evolve independently (are uncorrelated), hence $\langle \zeta_{\mathbf{k}} \zeta_{\mathbf{k}'} \rangle = \frac{H^2}{a^2\dot{\phi}^2} [\langle Q_{\mathbf{k}}^{vac} Q_{\mathbf{k}'}^{vac} \rangle + \langle Q_{\mathbf{k}}^s Q_{\mathbf{k}'}^s \rangle]$. We evolve individual terms separately, and then compute the power spectrum. We shall write the final form, the detailed calculations are in [44].

Power Spectrum

The Power spectrum is derived to be (as mentioned earlier, we get the PS from the 2-pt correlation of ζ)

$$P_{\zeta}(k) = \mathcal{P} \left(\frac{k}{k_0}\right)^{n_s-1} [1 + \mathcal{P}f_2(\xi)e^{4\pi\xi}]. \quad (2.66)$$

⁸Remember that $\zeta \sim -H\frac{\delta\phi}{\dot{\phi}}$, hence the inverse decay process evidently contributes to non-Gaussianity.

Where $\mathcal{P} = \frac{H^4}{4\pi^2\phi^2}$, and $f_2(\xi)$ is a dimensionless constant depending on the source terms and for large ξ , it can be approximated as

$$f_2(\xi) = \frac{7.5 \cdot 10^{-5}}{\xi^6}, \xi \gg 1 \quad (2.67)$$

The power spectrum is exponentially sensitive to ξ and it has to be $\mathcal{O}(1)$ to not affect the nature of the power spectrum.

Bispectrum

Similar to the power spectrum, the bispectrum contribution can also be computed just by taking the 3-pt correlation function of $\zeta_{\mathbf{k}}$, and we can then estimate an analytical form,

$$\langle \zeta_{\mathbf{k}_1} \zeta_{\mathbf{k}_2} \zeta_{\mathbf{k}_3} \rangle = \frac{3}{10} (2\pi)^{5/2} \mathcal{P}^3 e^{6\pi\xi} \frac{\delta(\mathbf{k}_1 + \mathbf{k}_2 + \mathbf{k}_3)}{k^6} \frac{1 + x_2^3 + x_3^3}{x_2^3 x_3^3} f_3(\xi, x_2, x_3); \quad x_i = \frac{k_i}{k}. \quad (2.68)$$

The δ function is for the momenta conservation and the bispectrum is different from zero only if $\sum_i \vec{k}_i = 0$. The bispectrum peaks for equilateral shape (owing to secondary field interaction, see Chapter 4), and for $x_1 = x_2 = 0$, we get an approximated expression for f_3 as

$$f_3(\xi, 1, 1) = \frac{2.8 \cdot 10^{-7}}{\xi^9}; \quad \xi \gg 1 \quad (2.69)$$

One can also define an effective momentum dependent f_{NL} parameter [48] and then evaluate it for $P_\zeta = 22 \cdot 10^{-10}$ and using the above equation of f_3 ,

$$f_{NL}^{eff}(\xi, x_1, x_2) = \frac{f_3(\xi x_1, x_2) \mathcal{P}^3 e^{6\pi\xi}}{\mathcal{P}_\zeta^2} \quad (2.70)$$

$$f_{NL}^{eq}|_{CMB} \approx 5.7 \cdot 10^{-10} \mathcal{P}^3 \frac{e^{6\pi\xi}}{\xi^9}. \quad (2.71)$$

CMB constrains $f_{NL} \leq 100$, and from this we deduce $\xi_{CMB} \leq 2.55$. For a quadratic potential of type $V(\phi) = \frac{1}{2}m^2\phi^2$, we get a bound for the coupling as $\frac{\alpha}{f} \leq 32$. There is a stronger constraint on ξ from (P)-reheating [47] as $\xi \leq 2.22$. One of the future goals of this thesis is to constrain ξ by analysing the late-time non-Gaussian effects using matter density PDF. To arrive at the PDF, we first begin by computing the ζ map during U(1) inflation for a particular value of ξ and $\frac{\alpha}{f}$ using Lattice Simulations, and later turn to computing the cumulants.

Chapter 3

Lattice Simulations

3.1 Introduction

Lattice simulations relies on discretising the background into a cubic lattice with comoving lattice spacing $\Delta x = \frac{L}{N}$, where L is the physical size of the box and there are N^3 points in the volume. We can then assign N^3 values to each point in the lattice to a continuous function $f(x)$ describing a field, such that

$$f(\vec{x}); x \in \mathbb{R}^3 \rightarrow f(\vec{n}), n \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, N\}. \quad (3.1)$$

We assume the lattice to be periodic, hence $f(N, n_2, n_3) = f(1, n_2, n_3)$. We do not split into the background and the perturbation part unlike the analytical framework [24]. The inflaton field is evolved along with the Euler-Lagrange EOM, the usual Klein-Gordon equation as

$$\frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial \tau^2} + 2\mathcal{H} \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial \tau} - \nabla^2 \phi + a^2 \frac{\partial V}{\partial \phi} = 0. \quad (3.2)$$

The above equation is discretised and is associated with N^3 points to the inflaton field,

$$\frac{\partial^2 \phi(\vec{n})}{\partial \tau^2} + 2\mathcal{H} \frac{\partial \phi(\vec{n})}{\partial \tau} - [\nabla^2 \phi](\vec{n}) + a^2 \frac{\partial V}{\partial \phi}(\vec{n}) = 0. \quad (3.3)$$

Eq 3.3 constitutes a set of N^3 ordinary differential equations (ODEs), one for each lattice point $\phi(\vec{n})$. These equations are coupled to each other through the discrete Laplacian $\nabla^2 \phi(\vec{n})$. The entire framework relies on semi-classical approximation. The modes are evolved from subhorizon to superhorizon scales during inflation but considering just the classical evolution, this means that the action is dominated by the classical path and do not consider quantum corrections. The latter effects are subdominant in the initial few e-folds of inflation [24, 49].

To compensate for this, we consider inflaton to be a stochastic random field and it turns out to be a good approximation, owing to the large occupation number. In the code,

the gradient term ($\frac{\partial\phi}{\partial x^i}$) is evaluated as: $[\frac{\partial\phi}{\partial x^i}](\vec{n}) = -\phi(\vec{n})[\nabla^2\phi](\vec{n})$. The definition of the Laplacian is used to evolve both the equations and their derivatives. Moreover, evaluating the Laplacian is computationally less expensive than computing the absolute value of the gradient term. [24, 27]

3.2 Lattice Simulations of U(1) Axion Inflation

To obtain the ζ map, we use the simulation developed by [24, 26]. We discuss below the equations and the methodology used to obtain the map, for details, refer to [24].

For the U(1) Axion inflation, we begin with the equation of motion for the field, with the source term included as in Eq. 2.62. In conformal time, it reads,

$$\phi'' + 2\mathcal{H}\phi' - \nabla^2\phi + a^2\frac{\partial V}{\partial\phi} = -a^2\frac{\alpha}{4f}F_{\mu\nu}\tilde{F}^{\mu\nu}. \quad (3.4)$$

The equations of motion for the gauge field is

$$\partial_\rho(\sqrt{-g}F^{\rho\sigma}) + \frac{\alpha}{f}\partial_\rho(\sqrt{-g}\tilde{F}^{\rho\sigma}) = 0. \quad (3.5)$$

The perturbation in the metric is not considered since $\delta\phi\delta g_{\mu\nu}$ do not contribute significantly. Metric perturbations are slow-roll suppressed in the present case as long as $\frac{\alpha}{f} \gg \frac{\phi'}{\mathcal{H}} \gg \sqrt{\epsilon}$, which is assumed throughout the thesis. The decoupling of $\delta g_{\mu\nu}$ from the $\delta\phi$ at all orders is an assumption when working with models of inflation involving significant amount of non-Gaussianity [24] The above equations are solved for each component after fixing the gauge using the Lorenz gauge condition as

$$\partial_\mu A^\mu = 0 \implies a^2\partial_0 A_0 = \partial_i A_i. \quad (3.6)$$

With this gauge, each equation is solved after assigning N^3 values to $\phi(\vec{n})$ and 4 components of $A_0(\vec{n}); A_i(\vec{n})$. And then the $5N^3$ equations are computed along with the time derivatives using the fourth order Runge-Kutta method [24]. The equations are then discretised but the gauge condition is not implicit and need to be verified at every stage. In the next section, we describe the results of the simulation and the statistics of ζ .

3.3 Results

3.3.1 ζ Map and Initial Conditions

We begin with considering the quadratic potential of the form

$$V = \frac{1}{2}m^2\phi^2, \quad (3.7)$$

with $m = 0.51 \cdot 10^{-5}$. This kind of quadratic potential is generated in string theory realizations of monodromy inflation but disfavoured by Planck results [50]. In fact, even

Figure 3.1: 3D map of normalised curvature perturbation ζ for the gaussian case on the left and U(1) Axion inflation on the right computed at the end of the simulation ($t = t_{end}$). It is equivalent to show this plot for $\delta\phi$ and for ζ , as we normalize by the standard deviation.

natural inflation of the cosine form potential described for $\phi \ll f$, can be Taylor expanded to a quadratic potential with the mass a function of $\left(\frac{\Lambda}{f}\right)$. However, the present analysis is independent of the potential as long as it satisfies the slow-roll condition.

The background values are set as : $\phi_{in} = -14.5$, $\bar{\phi}' = -0.8152m$. The simulation begins $N_e = 53$ e-folds before the end of inflation (≈ 7 e-folds to match with the CMB scales), and the simulation is run for $N^3 = 256$ points along each axis, and comoving length $L = \frac{2}{m}$. For these values, the lattice modes are $\kappa_{min} = 0.6H_i$ and $\kappa_{max} = 118H_i$ where H_i is the inflationary Hubble parameter at the beginning of the simulation. We consider $\frac{\alpha}{f} = 42$ and plan to perform the analysis for $\frac{\alpha}{f} = 40$ in the future. At the end of the simulation, the modes are of superhorizon scale.

3.3.2 PDF of ζ and statistics

We first begin by plotting the 3D map of the curvature perturbation ζ normalised by its standard deviation ($\zeta \equiv -H(\frac{\phi-\bar{\phi}}{\sigma})$). We can then compare the same map with an almost scale-invariant and Gaussian single scalar field inflation. Figure 3.1 shows the 3D map for $256*256*256$ elements, normalised by σ . The figure on the left is for the Gaussian case, which shows near-scale invariance, while on the right, we see the non-Gaussian case of U(1) Axion inflation. There is an obvious enhancement in the number of over-density points that is translated to the extended tail towards the right in the PDF. This is also due to the fact that there is an additional $\delta\phi$ contribution from inverse-decay effect. This map contains data points of all higher order statistics, and not limited to just two or three point correlation function. We now use this box to plot and analyse the Probability distribution function (PDF), and compute higher order cumulants from it. To this end, we compute

Figure 3.2: Histogram of PDF for the U(1) Axion inflation model, normalised by σ . There is an extended tail end towards the right indicating Non-Gaussianity due to the gauge field interaction. The direction of the tail depends on the sign of $\bar{\phi}'$.

the connected part of the correlators in real space (see Chapter 4 for details) [24]

$$\kappa_3 = \frac{\langle \zeta^3 \rangle}{\sigma^3}, \quad (3.8)$$

$$\kappa_4 = \frac{\langle \zeta^4 \rangle - 3\sigma^4}{\sigma^4}, \quad (3.9)$$

$$\kappa_5 = \frac{\langle \zeta^5 \rangle - 10\sigma^2 \langle \zeta^3 \rangle}{\sigma^5}. \quad (3.10)$$

Computing these cumulants for our map, we get $\kappa_3 = 0.5816488$, $\kappa_4 = 0.974489$, $\kappa_5 = 2.167123$, and this shows that $\kappa_5 > \kappa_4 > \kappa_3 > 0.5$. Higher order cumulants have higher magnitude than the lower order ones at the final time! The fact that higher order cumulants get larger and larger is a sign that ζ sourced by the gauge field can not be seen as an expansion around a Gaussian distribution, hence just the 'local' type of non-Gaussianity is not sufficient to describe the entire physics, higher order cumulants and correlators become important. This is non-trivial and an important motivation to consider the effects of this on the late-time evolution of the universe, and that is one of the reasons to consider U(1) Axion inflation as a prototype for the framework in this thesis.

Also, the growth of the higher order cumulants implies bispectrum alone is not sufficient to describe the entirety of non-Gaussian effects on the structure formation. Trispectrum or higher order correlation functions description is needed and lattice simulations can in principle compute the primordial correlators [24, 26]. In general, we might interpret the result as follows: 2-point or 3-point correlation functions might not fully describe the statistics of ζ within the U(1) Axion inflation model, and one of the goals of this thesis is to compute the effect of higher order correlations using the late-time matter density PDF approach. In principle, we can compute cumulants of all orders and analyse their

growth. This will pave the way to understanding the contribution of PNG during the late-time evolution of the universe and eventually constrain inflationary parameters. Before computing the cumulants, we first need to generate the linear prediction of δ_m using transfer functions.

A note on Central Limit Theorem

A quick concern that might arise is about the validity of CLT when there are gauge fields coupled to the inflaton leading to non-Gaussianity. As mentioned, one can understand that the quantum fluctuations due to the single scalar field inflaton is Gaussian by thinking in terms of the ground state of free field QHO or by considering CLT owing to the randomness. In case of U(1)-Axion inflation, the presence of a gauge field and its perturbations modifies the usual vacuum part of the QHO by including the source term contribution and interaction. In this case, the inverse decay contributes to an additional $\delta\phi$. The potential term - if broadly considered as a measure of interactions, contains the usual self-coupling of the inflaton *and* the Chern-Simons interaction. This interaction tends to provide a small but finite deviation from the usual QHO framework and the Gaussian wavepacket description. But this should happen considering the bounds observationally - the power spectrum should retain its form and n_s should be nearly scale-invariant, needless to say, slow-roll approximation should be valid. Keeping this in mind, we get a bound on ξ and the modes that are excited mostly are $k < 2\xi aH$. Within this regime of interest, a small number of modes are excited (linearly with ξ). Increasing ξ and going beyond the usual constraint of ξ excites a larger number of modes and they ultimately due to CLT converge to a Gaussian distribution. So, considering a large number of modes/large ξ ($N \rightarrow \infty$ limit) should suppress non-Gaussianity due to CLT and that is precisely what is observed in [24].

Chapter 4

From Inflation to Large-scale Structure

Once inflation ends, the inflaton decays and rapidly oscillates at the minima, and this leads to the formation of the Standard model particles in an epoch known as reheating. The dynamics of reheating post U(1) Axion inflation is studied in [47, 51]. Post the reheating era, the standard radiation dominated epoch begins. We describe below the growth of sub-horizon perturbations during radiation and matter dominated era, and later give a brief introduction to Non-Gaussianity, both primordial and late-time.

4.1 Sub-horizon perturbations

As described in Chapter 2, the constituents in the universe can be modeled as an incompressible fluid, and the motion can be then described by the Navier-Stokes equations. We slightly modify the equations to account for the expansion of the universe - converting to comoving coordinates and including peculiar velocity into account when computing the proper velocity ($\mathbf{u} = aH\mathbf{r} + v_p$). Using $\rho_m = \bar{\rho}_m(1 + \delta_m)$ and $\frac{d\bar{\rho}_m}{dt} = -3H\bar{\rho}_m$, ($\bar{\rho}_m$ is the background density), we get

$$\frac{d\delta_m}{dt} = -(1 + \delta_m)\frac{1}{a}\nabla \cdot v_p. \quad (4.1)$$

The velocity equation becomes

$$\frac{d(aH)}{dt}\mathbf{r} + aH\frac{d\mathbf{r}}{dt} + \frac{dv_p}{dt} = -\frac{\nabla p}{a\bar{\rho}_m(1 + \delta_m)} - \frac{1}{a}\nabla\Phi, \quad (4.2)$$

Φ is the gravitational Poisson potential with both the background and perturbed part, and we finally have the Poisson equation,

$$\frac{1}{a^2}\nabla^2\Phi = 4\pi G\bar{\rho}_m\delta_m. \quad (4.3)$$

Combining the above gives the following equations for matter perturbations

$$\frac{\partial \delta_m}{\partial t} = -\frac{1}{a} \mathbf{v}_p \cdot \nabla \delta_m - (1 + \delta_m) \frac{1}{a} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}_p, \quad (4.4)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{v}_p}{\partial t} = -\frac{1}{a} (\mathbf{v}_p \cdot \nabla) \cdot \mathbf{v}_p - H \mathbf{v}_p - \frac{\nabla p}{a \bar{\rho}_m (1 + \delta_m)} - \frac{1}{a} \nabla \Phi, \quad (4.5)$$

$$\nabla^2 \Phi = 4\pi G a^2 \bar{\rho}_m \delta_m. \quad (4.6)$$

We then Fourier transform the above equations: considering the linear independence of fourier transformed components along with the fact that at linear order of perturbation theory phases of different modes do not interact with each other and remain random [52].

¹ We also keep only terms linear in order and ignore the rest,

$$\frac{\partial \delta_m}{\partial t} = -\frac{ik}{a} v_p, \quad (4.7)$$

$$\frac{\partial v_p}{\partial t} = -H v - \frac{ik}{a} \Phi, \quad (4.8)$$

$$-k^2 \Phi = 4\pi G a^2 \delta_m \bar{\rho}_m. \quad (4.9)$$

Vector perturbations (if chosen a Fourier mode along one direction), the components in other two spatial directions decay with time and decouple from scalar perturbations. Now, substituting 4.7 in 4.8 and using $\frac{da}{dt} = aH$, we get

$$\frac{\partial^2 \delta_m}{\partial t^2} = -2H \frac{\partial \delta_m}{\partial t} + 4\pi G \delta_m \bar{\rho}_m. \quad (4.10)$$

This does not explicitly depend on 'k', we can then use separation of variables and see that,

$$\delta_m(k, t) = \delta_{m+}(k) D_+(t) + \delta_{m-}(k) D_-(t). \quad (4.11)$$

Where $D_{\pm}(t)$ are two linearly independent functions describing the growth or decay of perturbations, and since only one of the functions grow in time and contribute to structure formation, we shall only consider $D_+(t)$.

We shall show the form of the growth functions for the Einstein-deSitter case and the Radiation epoch, and then describe Transfer functions that transfer our initial ζ to δ_m .

¹Modes from inflation are random in the sense that they are picked out of the flat distribution $\phi \in [0, 2\pi]$ and at the linear order evolve independently due to homogeneity. They are coherent and in synchrony due to inflationary expansion, but they soon become acausal and do not interact until much later, deep into the structure formation era.

Einstein-deSitter

We have $\Omega_m = 1$ and $a \propto t^{2/3}$ with $H = \frac{2}{3t}$; $\bar{\rho}_m = \frac{1}{6\pi G t^2}$, the growth equation then takes the form

$$\ddot{D} = -\frac{4}{3t}\dot{D} + \frac{2}{3t^2}D. \quad (4.12)$$

This is a ODE with two solutions each for the growing mode and the decaying mode as $D_+ \propto t^{\frac{2}{3}}$ and $D_- \propto t^{-1}$, hence, the growth function grows with the scale factor during matter domination era.

Radiation epoch

Intuitively speaking, we would expect slower growth of matter during radiation dominated era due to the pressure component slowing it down. For $a \propto t^{1/2}$ and $H = \frac{1}{2t}$, we have

$$\ddot{D} = -\frac{1}{t}D. \quad (4.13)$$

This is an ODE with the solution $D_+ \propto \ln t = 2 \ln a$, and $D_- = 1$, the growth is logarithmic in time.

4.1.1 Superhorizon scales and Transfer Functions

To derive the relationship between ζ and δ_m , we closely follow the derivation in [53]. We begin with the fact that to a linear order in curvature K – a closed universe is a perturbation to a flat universe with a large radius of curvature R , and with spatial curvature corresponding to $-\frac{2}{3}\nabla^2\zeta$. We consider only superhorizon modes which are outside the horizon until radiation-matter equality.

The above approach provides an insight (a rather obvious one) - K and ζ both describe the curvature of the spatial geometry in the universe. (The differences are that K is a non-dynamic global parameter not taking into account of the perturbative/quantum effects unlike ζ . And since perturbations are always formed due to quantum fluctuations $\zeta \sim \delta\phi$ cannot be zero)².

We have from the first Friedmann equation,

$$H^2 + \frac{K}{a^2} = \frac{8\pi G\rho_0}{3a^3}, \quad (4.14)$$

and so

$$dt = \left[\frac{8\pi G\rho_0}{3a^3} - \frac{K}{a^2} \right]^{-1/2} \frac{da}{a}, \quad (4.15)$$

and this approximately to the leading order in K , is

$$dt \approx \sqrt{\frac{3}{8\pi G\rho_0}} \left[1 + \frac{3Ka}{16\pi G\rho_0} \right] a^{1/2} da, \quad (4.16)$$

²In a comoving gauge this can be equated to be zero with only the metric perturbations which in-turn has ζ , hence perturbations due to fluctuations are inevitable due to QM effects.

and with the initial condition that $t = 0, a = 0$, we get,

$$t \approx \frac{1}{\sqrt{6\pi G\rho}} \left[1 + \frac{9K}{80\pi G\rho_0} a \right]. \quad (4.17)$$

We now solve for ρ and we arrive at

$$\rho \approx \frac{1}{6\pi G t^2} \left[1 + \frac{9K}{80\pi G\rho_0} a \right]^2 \approx \frac{1}{6\pi G t^2} \left[1 + \frac{9K}{40\pi G\rho_0} a \right]. \quad (4.18)$$

Hence, δ_m is the term in the bracket,

$$\delta_m = \frac{9K}{40\pi G\rho_0} a = \frac{9(-\frac{2}{3}\nabla^2\zeta)}{40\pi G\rho_0} a = \boxed{-\frac{2\nabla^2\zeta}{5\Omega_m H_0^2} a} \quad (4.19)$$

where $\rho_0 = \frac{3\Omega_m H_0^2}{8\pi G}$ and the scale factor in the expression corresponds to the growth function during matter dominated epoch. Finally, we note that this assumption is only valid for superhorizon modes, and for subhorizon, due to radiation and baryonic effects, it is modified as

$$\tilde{\delta}_m(\mathbf{k}, a) = \frac{2k^2}{5\Omega_m H_0^2} \tilde{\zeta}(k) T(k) D_+(a) \quad (4.20)$$

Where we have reverted back to fourier space, with the \sim to differentiate the real space component from fourier space, and $T(k)$ is the transfer function taking the subhorizon physics into account and $T(k) \rightarrow 1$ on large scales.

4.2 Results

To arrive at δ_m from our ζ map and taking into account the $T(k)$ due to Baryonic physics, we use the Einstein-Boltzmann code CLASS. It is used in general to simulate the evolution of linear perturbations in the universe and to compute large scale structure observables [54]. We use it to compute the transfer functions and the matter power spectrum for comoving length $L = 1 \text{ Mpc}$, $L = 1000 \text{ Mpc}$, $L = 4634 \text{ Mpc}$. We show the results in Figure 4.1. Each value at a lattice point is just linearly scaled, and the visibility depends on the length of the box we consider, 4.1(a) closely resembles the ζ map, as expected.

The matter power spectrum is proportional to the primordial power spectrum similar to the way δ_m is.

$$P_\zeta(k) = \frac{2\pi^2 A_s}{k^3} \left(\frac{k}{k^*} \right)^{n_s-1}. \quad (4.21)$$

Where A_s is a constant independent of 'k', and k^* is the CMB pivot scale. According to Planck CMB measurement [37], $A_s = (2.10 \pm 0.03) \times 10^{-9}$, with $k^* = 0.05 \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$. The matter power spectrum is

$$P_{\delta_m}(k) = \frac{4k^4}{25(\Omega_m H_0^2)^2} [T(k)]^2 [D_+(a)]^2 P_\zeta(k). \quad (4.22)$$

(a) 3D map of δ_m : comoving length $L = 1$ Mpc(b) 3D map of δ_m : $L = 1000$ Mpc

Figure 4.1: 3D map of δ_m normalised by σ after applying the transfer function and the growth factor to the primordial ζ of U(1) Axion inflation model.

(a) PDF Histogram

(b) Matter Power Spectrum.

Figure 4.2: To the left: Histogram of the PDF of both δ_m and ζ , we see that they almost perfectly overlap as expected except some noise at the peak, and both having an extended tail on the right. To the right: Matter Power Spectrum using CLASS.

Usually one considers the dimensionless Power spectrum ³,

$$\Delta_{\delta_m} = \sqrt{\frac{k^3 P_{\delta_m}(k)}{(2\pi)^2}} = \frac{4}{5} \sqrt{A_s} \frac{k^2}{k_{eq}^2} T(k) \frac{D_+(a)}{a_{eq}} \left(\frac{k}{k^*}\right)^{(n_s-1)/2}, \quad (4.23)$$

where the subscript 'eq' refers to matter-radiation equality. This shows the variation with respect to 'k' for superhorizon ($T(k) \rightarrow 1$). For subhorizon scale, the above equation is modified as,

$$\sqrt{\frac{k^3 P_{\delta_m}(k)}{(2\pi)^2}} \approx 9.8 \sqrt{A_s} \ln \frac{k}{k_{eq}} T(k) \frac{D_+(a)}{a_{eq}} \left(\frac{k}{k^*}\right)^{(n_s-1)/2}. \quad (4.24)$$

The power spectrum (density perturbations per logarithmic wavenumber) increases logarithmically for high 'k' and drops as $\propto k^2$ going to zero for small 'k'. This is expected, there should be no 'communication' on superhorizon scales and within the horizon, for the most part is radiation dominated and the growth is logarithmic, and this is noticed in 4.2(b).

We can further compute the cumulants from the PDF, as we did in subsection 3.3.2, not surprisingly, there is not much enhancement from higher orders since there is no significant structure formation. We find that $\kappa_3 = 0.618036$, $\kappa_4 = 1.0689340$ and $\kappa_5 = 2.458635$, there is a slight increase from that of ζ with the same trend of $\kappa_5 > \kappa_4 > \kappa_3$.

4.3 Non-Gaussianity and Structure formation

Now that we have obtained the δ_m map, before further analysis, we briefly describe different types of non-Gaussianity, how to quantify them and then proceed to understand the formation of non-Gaussianity in the late-time evolution of the universe.

Deviations from Gaussian initial conditions provides information about inflaton's interactions with possible other degrees of freedom. These PNG features helps distinguish inflation models which would yield the same predictions for scalar spectral index n_s [16].

4.3.1 Primordial Non-Gaussianity

Consider a random field $f(\mathbf{x})$, the Fourier transform of the field is

$$f(x) = \int \frac{d^3k}{(2\pi)^3} f(\mathbf{k}) e^{i\mathbf{k}\mathbf{x}}. \quad (4.25)$$

We can parameterise the field as complex components $f(\mathbf{k}) = a_{\mathbf{k}} + ib_{\mathbf{k}}$. Now, if the field is Gaussian random, then there is an additional constraint on the form of the Probability distribution function (PDF) of the field in either real or Fourier space,

$$\mathcal{P}(a_{\mathbf{k}}, b_{\mathbf{k}}) = \frac{1}{\pi \sigma_k^2} e^{\left[-\frac{a_{\mathbf{k}}^2 + b_{\mathbf{k}}^2}{\sigma_k^2}\right]}. \quad (4.26)$$

³This is useful since in 3D, there are a lot of wavevectors \vec{k} for a given k .

We can always generalise and substitute back $f(\mathbf{k})$ based on its form. In that case the PDF is a functional depending on $f(\mathbf{k})$. Also, the variance only depends on the magnitude 'k' since we are assuming statistical isotropy.

The expectation value of a functional can be computed as $\langle A[f(\mathbf{x})] \rangle = \int dx A[f(x)]\mathcal{P}(x)$. The expectation value of a two-point correlation function for a Gaussian field depends on the variance of the field, which we call the power spectrum. Due to Wick's theorem, every higher point correlation can be written in terms of the variance, as previously mentioned in Chapter 1.

Primordial Non-Gaussianity (PNG) of the equilateral type (a signature of U(1) Axion inflation, more on this in the below sections) might arise due to interactions between the inflaton and other fields (there are other ways to generate PNG, for e.g., if the quantum fluctuations were not in the vacuum state). These interactions imply a need to go beyond the power spectrum.

Bispectrum

Fourier transform of a 3-point correlation function of ζ gives the bispectrum, the leading non-Gaussian signature,

$$\langle \zeta_{\mathbf{k}_1} \zeta_{\mathbf{k}_2} \zeta_{\mathbf{k}_3} \rangle = (2\pi)^3 B_\zeta(k_1, k_2, k_3) \delta(\mathbf{k}_1 + \mathbf{k}_2 + \mathbf{k}_3). \quad (4.27)$$

It is easy to see how ζ quantifies non-Gaussianity, remember that it measures the time delay at different parts for inflation to end, and we can think of ζ as a clock or as a Goldstone boson, and it is gauge-invariant.

Due to statistical isotropy and homogeneity, we consider only the magnitude 'k' in B_ζ , and the delta distribution is for 3-momentum conservation, the momentum must form a triangle. B_ζ is a homogeneous function of degree -6 for scale-invariant fluctuations $B_\zeta(\lambda k_1, \lambda k_2, \lambda k_3) = \lambda^{-6} B_\zeta(k_1, k_2, k_3)$ (If $\{\tau, x\} \rightarrow \lambda\{\tau, x\}$, then $\zeta_{\mathbf{k}} \rightarrow \lambda^3 \zeta_{\mathbf{k}}$, as $\zeta \sim \delta t$, then B_ζ should depend on the inverse 6th power to maintain scale-invariance).

Further, rotational invariance implies that we only need to consider the ratio of the two modes: $x_2 = \frac{k_2}{k_1}; x_3 = \frac{k_3}{k_1}$.

The bispectrum can be represented in terms of the "Shape function" as

$$B_\zeta(k_1, k_2, k_3) = \frac{S(k_1, k_2, k_3)}{(k_1 k_2 k_3)^2} k^{*6} P_\zeta^2(k^*), \quad (4.28)$$

Where k^* is the pivot scale. The shape of the bispectrum refers to the dependence of S on the momentum ratios $\frac{k_2}{k_1}; \frac{k_3}{k_1}$ while fixing the overall momentum scale $K \equiv \frac{1}{3}(k_1 + k_2 + k_3)$. The running of the bispectrum refers to the dependence of the bispectrum on the overall momentum K , while keeping the ratios fixed. We can finally define the f_{NL} parameter as

$$f_{NL} = \frac{5}{18} S(K, K, K) = \frac{5}{18} \frac{B_\zeta(k, k, k)}{P_\zeta^2(k)}. \quad (4.29)$$

Figure 4.3: Different momentum configurations of the bispectrum. Credits [1]

Local Non-Gaussianity

One way to parameterise Non-Gaussianity is to Taylor expand around the Gaussian field, (that's why it is called 'local') and including the non-linear terms. So expanding ζ around the Gaussian ζ_g ⁴,

$$\zeta(\mathbf{x}) = \zeta_g(\mathbf{x}) + \frac{3}{5} f_{NL}^{local} [\zeta_g^2(\mathbf{x}) - \langle \zeta_g^2 \rangle]. \quad (4.30)$$

The bispectrum is then

$$B_\zeta(k_1, k_2, k_3) = \frac{6}{5} f_{NL}^{local} \times [P_\zeta(k_1)P_\zeta(k_2) + P_\zeta(k_2)P_\zeta(k_3) + P_\zeta(k_3)P_\zeta(k_1)] \quad (4.31)$$

$$= \frac{6}{5} f_{NL}^{local} \frac{\Delta_\zeta^4}{(k_1 k_2 k_3)^3} \left(\frac{k_1^2}{k_2 k_3} + \frac{k_2^2}{k_1 k_3} + \frac{k_3^2}{k_1 k_2} \right); \quad \Delta_\zeta^2(k) = \frac{P_\zeta(k)}{k^3}, \quad (4.32)$$

The shape function takes the form $S_{local}(k_1, k_2, k_3) = \frac{1}{3} \left(\frac{k_3^2}{k_1 k_2} + P.. \right)$, where 'P' refers to the other permutations, in the limit of a longest wavelength, with $k_1 \ll k_2 \approx k_3$, we get the squeezed limit $S_{local}(k_1, k_2, k_3) = \frac{2k_2}{3k_1}$

Equilateral Non-Gaussianity

Equilateral type Non-Gaussianity is when $k_1 \approx k_2 \approx k_3$ and can arise when there are higher derivative interactions or multi-field inflation, similar to U(1) Axion Inflation. Derivative

⁴In case of multi-field inflation, we can quantify non-Gaussianity using the δN formalism. We measure the number of e-folds difference between two different parts in terms of ζ , where at $t = t_{ini}$, ζ is measured on flat hypersurface and at $t = t_{fin}$, it is measured on uniform density hypersurface. This δN can be Taylor expanded to provide a relationship between ζ and $\delta\phi^I$. The product $\zeta\delta\phi^I$ can result in a form of PNG as well [55]. Importantly, $\delta\phi^I$ can be Gaussian but the expansion renders ζ non-Gaussian.

interactions are suppressed when any individual mode is far outside the horizon [1]. The shape function takes the form,

$$S_{eq}(k_1, k_2, k_3) = \left(\frac{k_1}{k_2} + P\dots \right) - \left(\frac{k_1^2}{k_2 k_3} + P\dots \right) - 2. \quad (4.33)$$

For the U(1) Axion inflation, as previously mentioned in (2.69 - 2.71), $f_{NL}^{eq} \equiv \frac{f_3(\xi;1,1)\mathcal{P}^3 e^{6\pi\xi}}{(P_\zeta(k))^2}$ [44]. This contribution comes from the sourced term due to the gauge field. From the WMAP data, there is a constraint on f_{NL}^{eq} as $-214 < f_{NL}^{eq} < 266$, this in-turn as stated before constrains $\xi \leq 2.65$ [56]. In this thesis we consider $\xi \approx 2.6$ to lie within the bounds but enough to investigate the effect of PNG contribution. The bispectrum from Axion inflation, although is very similar to the equilateral template, the two shapes are not identical [44]. There is also a small but finite orthogonal Non-Gaussianity contribution for a certain range : $x_2 \approx x_3 \approx \frac{1}{2}$.

4.3.2 Perturbation Theory

Linear and Non-Linear PT

To describe non-Gaussianity during structure formation, we return to the equations describing the dynamics of δ_m . (remember $\zeta \rightarrow \delta_m$). We begin with an alternative way of writing the perturbation equations (4.4-4.6) using the phase space coordinates, where the distribution function $f(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{x}, t)$ is used to compute the density field, peculiar velocity field, etc. Phase space conservation for particle number density (indirectly the Liouville theorem) is the Vlasov equation written as

$$\frac{df}{dt} = \frac{\partial f}{\partial t} + \frac{\mathbf{p}}{ma} \nabla f - am \nabla \Phi \frac{\partial f}{\partial \mathbf{p}} = 0. \quad (4.34)$$

Non-linearity is inherent here owing to the 'poisson equation - density - distribution function' relationship. The zeroth moment of the distribution function ($\int d^3\mathbf{p} f(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{x}, t) \equiv \rho(\mathbf{x}, t)$) gives the matter density field, the first moment is $\rho(\mathbf{x}, t)\mathbf{v}_p$, and so on. The moments of the Vlasov equation in turn results in the usual continuity equation (zeroth moment, Eq. 4.4), Euler equation (first moment, Eq. 4.5).⁵

Primordial non-Gaussian signature during structure formation is captured via the Poisson equation relationship, $\zeta \rightarrow \Phi$ and this in turn is related to δ_m as seen in Eq 4.6.

Structure formation is a positive feedback loop process of overdense regions becoming even denser. This type of growth in the formation of structures motivates a perturbative expansion of the overdensity parameter, since the physics is scale-dependent. The regions which can 'communicate' to other overdense regions slowly gravitate close to each other. The

⁵Considering the particle number density conservation and the variation of f with time and space, with further imposing that the volume is infinitesimal, we arrive at 4.4 and 4.5.

perturbation theory captures this and assumption relies on expansion of the overdensity (δ_m) or the velocity field (\mathbf{v}) about the linear term,

$$\delta_m = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \delta_m^{(n)}(\mathbf{x}, t); \quad \mathbf{v} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \mathbf{v}^{(n)}(\mathbf{x}, t). \quad (4.35)$$

We now Fourier transform the perturbed field in linear order (recall $\tilde{f}(k, t) = \int \frac{d^3\mathbf{x}}{(2\pi)^3} e^{-i\mathbf{k}\mathbf{x}} f(\mathbf{x}, t)$) and we arrive at the continuity and momentum equations for perturbed quantities in linear order. For overdensity it reads [5]

$$\frac{\partial \tilde{\delta}_m}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{v}}_p = - \int d^3\mathbf{k}_1 d^3\mathbf{k}_2 \delta_D(\mathbf{k} - (\mathbf{k}_1 + \mathbf{k}_2)) \frac{(\mathbf{k}_1 + \mathbf{k}_2) \cdot \mathbf{k}_1}{k_1^2} \tilde{\mathbf{v}}_p(\mathbf{k}_1, t) \tilde{\delta}_m(\mathbf{k}_1, t). \quad (4.36)$$

We can also consider the scale factor or the growth factor (the above expansion is with a time-independent coefficient) into the perturbation expansion equation on the RHS. Note that there is non-linearity in the above equation through mode coupling (due to $\nabla \cdot ((1 + \delta_m)\mathbf{v}_p)$ term in the continuity equation), and this in-turn leads to non-linearity even in the first order in perturbation theory. Non-Gaussianity in structure formation is inevitable since gravity acts non-linearly: due to these mode couplings and higher order perturbation couplings (The rate at which particles move into the overdense region depends on the overdensity implies positive feedback loop/hierarchical structure formation).

The equation of motion in Fourier space provides us with the following form

$$\delta_n(\mathbf{k}) = \int d^3\mathbf{q}_1 \dots \int d^3\mathbf{q}_n \delta_D(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{q}_{1\dots n}) F_n(\mathbf{q}_1 \dots \mathbf{q}_n) \delta_1(\mathbf{q}_1) \delta_2(\mathbf{q}_2) \dots \delta_n(\mathbf{q}_n). \quad (4.37)$$

This is the usual perturbation theory expansion solved by the expansion in 4.34, and in the first order, it gives us the continuity and Euler equation. The kernel F_n is equivalent to the Green's function in Path integral formalism. LSS as mentioned from initial small structures form in an hierarchical fashion. Overdense regions coalesce and evolve faster than underdense regions, and overtime δ_m value goes beyond $\mathcal{O}(1)$, and perturbation theory breaks down. Further, the structure virializes at around a critical $\delta_c \approx 1.68$.

There are two main assumptions in consideration when solving the equations during structure formation. One is that that in the linear order, we have $\sigma_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, t) = 0$, no anisotropic stresses and this is called single flow approximation. This implies that the velocity dispersion is negligible, the flow is dominated by the velocity gradient due to the overdensity. This approximation breaks down when there is shell crossing so we also assume no shell-crossing. This means the flows do not overlap in phase space. The crossing occurs as different flows are pulled closer due to gravity and the velocity at a point has no singular value. Figure 4.4 depicts the shell-crossing and eventual formation of multiple flows when the linear approximation breaks down. ⁶

⁶In short we assume $[\delta_m(\mathbf{x}, t), u_i(\mathbf{x}, t)]_{,i} = [u_i(\mathbf{x}, t), u_j(\mathbf{x}, t)]_{,j} = 0$

Figure 4.4: Description of shell-crossings and multi-flow regions in phase space. Credits [5].

Statistics of perturbation theory

Uncertainty in the distribution of initial quantum fluctuations enforces a stochastic viewpoint and the need for a statistical analysis. During inflation, the fluctuations are stretched to superhorizon scales, and then the field can be treated as a classical stochastic field. In this way, its ensemble average is equal to its vacuum expectation value [5].

A random field is called statistically homogeneous if all the joint multi-point probability distribution functions $p(\delta_1, \delta_2, \dots)$ or its moments, (ensemble averages of the product of densities), remain the same under translation, and statistically isotropic if the PDFs are invariant under spatial rotations.

Given a random variable X , we can define the n^{th} moment as

$$\mu_n = \langle X^n \rangle = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x^n \mathcal{P}_X(x) dx. \quad (4.38)$$

The probability distribution function (more on this in the next chapter) $\mathcal{P}_X(x)$ is normalised. The mean is the first moment $\mu_1 = \langle X \rangle = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x \mathcal{P}_X(x) dx$, and this can always be made 0 by defining the central moment with the mean subtracted off. ($\mu_1 = \langle X \rangle = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (x - \langle X \rangle) \mathcal{P}_X(x) dx$). The variance is the second central moment : $\sigma^2 = \mu_2 = \langle (X - \langle X \rangle)^2 \rangle$.

In LSS Cosmology, it is convenient to compute the connected moments written in terms of the N-point correlation function. The 2-point correlation function that we encountered earlier was sufficient to describe a Gaussian field but deviations from Gaussianity requires information from higher order of correlation functions. Any statistical ensemble can be written in terms of the connected parts at arbitrary number of locations,

$$\langle \delta(\mathbf{x}_1) \delta(\mathbf{x}_2) \dots \delta(\mathbf{x}_N) \rangle_c = \langle \delta(\mathbf{x}_1) \delta(\mathbf{x}_2) \dots \delta(\mathbf{x}_N) \rangle - \sum_{s \in \text{partition } \mathcal{P}} \prod_{s \in \mathcal{P}} \langle \delta(\mathbf{x}_{s1}) \delta(\mathbf{x}_{s2}) \dots \delta(\mathbf{x}_{s\#s}) \rangle. \quad (4.39)$$

Figure 4.5: Connected part of the moments. [5]

Figure 4.6: Connected moment expansion for the 3-point moment.

When the function is evaluated at one particular point, it results in the *cumulants* of different orders.

$$\langle \delta_1 \delta_2 \dots \delta_N \rangle_c = \langle \delta_1 \delta_2 \dots \delta_N \rangle - \sum_{s \in \text{partition } \mathcal{P} \{1,2,\dots,N\}} \prod_{s \in \mathcal{P}} \langle \delta_{s_1} \delta_{s_2} \dots \delta_{s_{\#s}} \rangle. \quad (4.40)$$

We write down the cumulants for overdensity for a few orders as,

$$\langle \delta \rangle_c = \langle \delta \rangle, \quad (4.41)$$

$$\langle \delta^2 \rangle_c = \sigma^2 = \langle \delta^2 \rangle - \langle \delta \rangle_c^2, \quad (4.42)$$

$$\langle \delta^3 \rangle_c = \langle \delta^3 \rangle - 3\langle \delta^2 \rangle_c \langle \delta \rangle_c - \langle \delta \rangle_c^3. \quad (4.43)$$

One advantage to the cumulant formalism is that it helps us to really compute the independent N-point functions. This is evident from Figure 4.6. For example, consider a two-point correlation function $\langle \delta(x_1) \delta(x_2) \rangle$. This in principle can be non-zero if $\delta(x_1) \sim \delta_1$ and δ_2 both are equal to the mean/background density, even though they are not "truly" correlated. This can be seen if we take $|x_1 - x_2| \rightarrow \infty$, and the correlations should die down, but the moments can still exist. Hence, the "true" correlations are in the connected part. As previously mentioned, we can always make the mean zero considering the central moment/cumulant formulation.

Smoothing

Perturbation theory (PT) breaks down in highly non-linear regimes, hence it is necessary to work within the domain of validity (implies scales of interest). Smoothing essentially 'smoothes' out the non-linear small scale regime within a given radius 'R', in which case we average the overdensity over a Window function over the radius of interest,

$$\delta(\mathbf{x})_{L,R} = \int_{|\mathbf{x}' - \mathbf{x}| < R} d^3 \mathbf{x} W_R(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}') \delta(\mathbf{x}')_L, \quad (4.44)$$

where the spherical top-hat window function (of interest for the thesis) takes the form $W(R, x) = \frac{3}{4\pi R^3} \Theta(R - |x|)$, $\Theta(x)$ is the Heaviside function. The short wavelength fluctuations inside the region of interest cancel each other. Note that all the correlation functions and smoothing happens at the same time 't', hence we do not write the time parameter explicitly ('equal-time correlation functions'). In the Fourier space, the variance is given by

$$\sigma_R^2 = \int \frac{d^3\mathbf{k}}{(2\pi)^3} \tilde{W}_{L,R}^2(\mathbf{k}) P_\delta(k). \quad (4.45)$$

The top-hat Window function in Fourier space is

$$W(k) = \frac{3}{(kR)^3} (\sin(kR) - (kR)\cos(kR)). \quad (4.46)$$

With this information at our disposal, we are ready to compute the cumulant generating function and the cumulants for the smoothed density field over different radii of interest in the next chapter.

Chapter 5

Probability Distribution and Cumulants

In this chapter, we give an introduction to the Probability distribution function, Cumulant Generating function and our analysis in this thesis using the Saddle-point approximation. We discuss in detail about the methodology implemented to finally arrive at the cumulants for both non-Gaussian (U(1) Axion inflation) and Gaussian case. Further, we also give an introduction to Large deviation theory. We then finally discuss the results obtained after computing the cumulants.

5.1 Cumulant Generating Function

If all the moments are finite (which may not be the case always), then we can define the Moment Generating Function $\psi(\lambda)$ (MGF) as

$$\psi(\lambda) \equiv \langle e^{\lambda X} \rangle = \int dx e^{\lambda x} \mathcal{P}(x) = \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\langle X^n \rangle}{n!} \lambda^n. \quad (5.1)$$

MGF can then be used to compute moments of all orders by differentiating it at zero, so

$$\langle X^n \rangle = \left. \frac{d^n \psi(\lambda)}{d\lambda^n} \right|_{\lambda=0}. \quad (5.2)$$

It is easier to theoretically predict MGF instead of the Probability distribution function (PDF), and the convergence of MGF is necessary for Central Limit Theorem to be valid [57]. We can then define the cumulant generating function (CGF) as the natural logarithm of the MGF,

$$\phi(\lambda) \equiv \ln \psi(\lambda) = \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\langle X^n \rangle_c}{n!} \lambda^n. \quad (5.3)$$

In this case the cumulants of all orders can be computed using the CGF. The n^{th} cumulant gives extra information not contained in any previous cumulant, as previously mentioned.

5.2 Probability Distribution Function

The Probability distribution function (PDF) can be computed by the inverse Laplace transform of the CGF, given by

$$P(x) = \int_{-i\infty}^{i\infty} \frac{dx}{2\pi i} e^{\lambda x + \phi(\lambda)}. \quad (5.4)$$

The above is an integral in the complex plane, we can then Wick rotate λ to arrive at the familiar Gaussian distribution. The above equation can be generalised to multi-dimensional PDF [5]

$$P(x_1, x_2 \dots x_n) = \int_{-i\infty}^{i\infty} \frac{dx_1}{2\pi i} \frac{dx_2}{2\pi i} \dots \frac{dx_n}{2\pi i} e^{(\sum_{q=1}^n \lambda_q x_q + \phi(\lambda_1 \dots \lambda_n))}. \quad (5.5)$$

5.2.1 Generating Functional and Propagators

We give a brief primer to generating functional before we proceed to discuss our analysis. Consider an n -dimensional random variable $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, x_2 \dots x_n)$, the moment generating functional is

$$\mathcal{Z}(\lambda) = \langle e^{\lambda \cdot \mathbf{x}} \rangle = \int \prod_{i=1}^n dx_i e^{\lambda \cdot \mathbf{x}} \mathcal{P}(x_i), \quad (5.6)$$

for $(\lambda_1, \lambda_2 \dots \lambda_n)$. We can further define the cumulant generating functional as $W(\lambda) = \ln \mathcal{Z}(\lambda)$. The n^{th} order moment is then

$$\left\langle \prod_{i=1}^n x_i \right\rangle = \frac{1}{\mathcal{Z}(0)} \prod_{i=1}^n \frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda_i} \mathcal{Z}(\lambda) \Big|_{\lambda=0}. \quad (5.7)$$

In the functional formalism, we move from summing over every probabilistic "value" \mathbf{x} can take to every probabilistic "path" / "curves" \mathbf{x} can traverse (in other words, all possible configurations), so we replace equation 5.6 by

$$\mathcal{Z}(\lambda) = \mathcal{N} \int \mathcal{D}\mathbf{x} e^{-S[\mathbf{x}] + \lambda \mathbf{x}}. \quad (5.8)$$

\mathcal{N} is a normalisation constant. We can indeed include $\lambda \mathbf{x}$ term inside the *action* $S[\mathbf{x}]$. $\mathcal{Z}[\lambda = 0, x]$ is the well-known "partition function" in statistical mechanics. We can further modify the above equation for \mathbf{x} that is a function of t ,

$$\mathcal{Z}(\lambda) = \mathcal{N} \int \mathcal{D}\mathbf{x} e^{-S[\mathbf{x}] + \int d^D x \lambda(t) \cdot \mathbf{x}(t)}, \quad (5.9)$$

To arrive at $\mathcal{P}(x)$ in terms of the *action*, we compute the normalisation constant at $\lambda = 0$ as

$$\mathcal{N}^{-1} = \int \mathcal{D}x \mathcal{P}(x) = \int \mathcal{D}x e^{-S[\mathbf{x}]}.$$
 (5.10)

The probability of \mathbf{x} taking a random value is now the functional amplitude *action* $S[\mathbf{x}]$ for a *field* \mathbf{x} to have the configuration $\mathbf{x}(t)$ [58].

5.3 Reduced CGF and Weakly Non-Gaussian Distributions

Mildly non-linear regimes would be of interest and will be considered throughout the work. Consider an initial Gaussian distribution after the gravity induced non-linearity, resulting in higher order cumulants as a function of variance σ^2 due to Wick's theorem. Recall from the diagrammatic representation of cumulants, given 'n' points, we need 'n-1' lines to connect them. For example, for $\langle \delta^3 \rangle_c$, we have three points, and we can connect two points by a line and this represents $\langle \delta^2 \rangle_c$, and remaining point can be connected to the two vertices in two ways, giving a contribution of $\langle \delta^2 \rangle_c^2$. This can be generalised to $\langle \delta^n \rangle_c \sim \sigma^{2n-2}$, whenever σ is small. (For a deeper physical insight due to the hierarchical nature of structure formation, see [59].)

Hence, in this regime we can define the reduced cumulant generating function as a function of the reduced cumulants $S_n = \frac{\langle \delta^n \rangle_c}{\sigma^{2n-2}}$ as

$$\phi(\lambda) = \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} S_n \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{n!} \lambda^n.$$
 (5.11)

We can then substitute in the form of S_n and we get

$$\phi(\lambda) = -\sigma^2 \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\langle \delta^n \rangle_c}{n!} \left(-\frac{\lambda}{\sigma^2} \right)^n.$$
 (5.12)

S_n remains approximately constant throughout the late-time gravitational evolution for Gaussian initial conditions or mildly non-linear scales [60, 61]. This evidently defines some sort of a scaling property of correlation functions [62]. The mean of a n-point correlation function in a given volume V is

$$\bar{\delta}_n(V) = \frac{1}{V_n} \int_V d^3r_1 d^3r_2 \dots d^3r_n \delta_n(r_1, r_2, \dots, r_n).$$
 (5.13)

Then the above equation is related to the two-point correlation function as $\bar{\delta}_n(V) = S_n [\bar{\delta}_2(V)]^{n-1}$.¹

¹This can be translated to the PDF description using the *ergodic* hypothesis.

It is also convenient to define the rescaled cumulants $\epsilon_n = \frac{\langle \delta^n \rangle_c}{\sigma^n} = \sigma^{n-2} S_n$, that are approximately independent of the smoothing scale [60].

To describe local non-Gaussianity using PDF formalism, one can substitute Eq.5.11 in Eq 5.4 and Taylor expand in terms close to the Gaussian distribution, called the Edgeworth expansion. Expanding $\phi(\lambda) \approx -\frac{\lambda^2}{2} + \frac{S_3}{3!} \lambda^3 + \dots$ and doing the same for the non-Gaussian part as well, and collecting the terms of the same order in σ , we obtain the so-called Edgeworth form of the Gram-Charlier series for the density PDF. [5]

5.4 Saddle-Point Approximation and Approach

Before we delve into Path integral formalism, we review the Laplace method which is the real plane equivalent of the Saddle point approximation.

5.4.1 Laplace Method

Consider the integral of the form

$$J = \int dx e^{-f(x)}. \quad (5.14)$$

If the function has a global minima such that $f''(x) > 0$, then the integral can be Taylor expanded around the minima,

$$f(x) \approx f(x^*) + \frac{f''(x^*)}{2} (x - x^*)^2, \quad (5.15)$$

the first order terms vanish owing to the minima requirement, we can then substitute the above form back in the integrand and we get,

$$J \approx e^{-f(x^*)} \int dx e^{\left(-\frac{f''(x^*)}{2} (x-x^*)^2\right)} = \sqrt{\frac{2\pi}{f''(x^*)}} e^{-f(x^*)}. \quad (5.16)$$

Laplace method can also be generalised to higher dimensions, we then approximate the function around its minima as,

$$f(\mathbf{x}) \approx f(\mathbf{x}^*) + \frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}^*)^T \mathbf{H}_f(\mathbf{x}^*) (\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}^*), \quad (5.17)$$

where \mathbf{H}_f is the Hessian Matrix at the minima given by $\left. \frac{\partial^2 f}{\partial x_i \partial x_j} \right|_{\mathbf{x}^*}$. The Hessian will be in the denominator in the square root for the higher dimensional equivalent integral approximation.

5.4.2 Spherical Collapse

To describe the non-linear gravitational evolution during structure formation, we take advantage of the rotational invariance (isotropy in the universe), and consider a symmetrical spherical configuration.

We consider a spherically symmetric over-density perturbation in a spatially flat universe during the matter-dominated epoch with $\Omega_m = 1$. We evolve the system, aiming to understand the dynamics inside a spherical shell of radius 'r' enclosing a total mass 'M', centered around the origin we freely choose at $\mathbf{x} = 0$. The mass is conserved due to Birkhoff's theorem (system is completely isolated within the spherical shell with Minkowskian metric at the asymptote). This is before shell-crossing.² The total energy ϵ is < 0 owing to the gravitational boundedness.

The kinetic and potential energy compensates each other, given by

$$\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{dr}{d\tau} \right)^2 - \frac{GM}{r} = \epsilon. \quad (5.18)$$

We can then parameterise into a variable θ and for the above equation, we arrive at

$$r = -\frac{GM}{2\epsilon}(1 - \cos(\theta)); \quad \tau = \frac{GM}{(-2\epsilon)^{3/2}}(\theta - \sin(\theta)). \quad (5.19)$$

One can think of θ as a rescaled conformal time, since we can solve the spherical collapse considering the region of interest as a closed universe ($r(\tau) \propto t^{2/3}$). The region we consider first expands due to \dot{r} , and then at $\theta = \pi$, it "sees" more and more over-dense region causing it to slow down and eventually collapse.

For an Einstein de-Sitter universe (EdS), and comoving radius of the shell $R(\tau) = \frac{r}{a(\tau)}$, we have,

$$a = \left(\frac{8\pi G}{3} \rho_i a_i^3 \right)^{1/3} \left(\frac{3}{2} \tau \right)^{2/3}. \quad (5.20)$$

Substituting for τ from Eq 5.19 in Eq 5.20, we can obtain the relationship between the scale factor and θ , similarly for the comoving radius 'R',

$$a = - \left(\frac{9}{2} \right)^{2/3} \frac{2\pi G}{3\epsilon} \rho_i a_i^3 r^2 (\theta - \sin(\theta))^{2/3}; \quad R = r \left(\frac{2}{9} \right)^{1/3} \frac{1 - \cos(\theta)}{(\theta - \sin(\theta))^{2/3}}. \quad (5.21)$$

We also have the following equation in terms of the density contrast,

$$1 + \delta(R) = \frac{3M}{4\pi r^3 \rho_i} \left(\frac{a^3}{a_i^3} \right) = \left(\frac{r_i}{R} \right)^3, \quad (5.22)$$

²One way to think of shell crossing here is to consider concentric shells centered at the same point, and then evolve the matter distribution inside the shells according to the spherical collapse formalism. After a certain time, the shells cross and there appears regions having multifold regions (multiple velocities at one point).

for some initial r_i . This just states that due to mass conservation, we can relate the ratio of the initial density to the final one in terms of the comoving radius or the scale factor. From the equations for 'R' and 'a', we arrive at,

$$\delta = \frac{9(\theta - \sin(\theta))^2}{2(1 - \cos(\theta))^3} - 1. \quad (5.23)$$

We now need to know the behaviour of initial overdensity within the shell and then relate that with the above equation. For that we Taylor expand θ and compute the initial ϵ_i from the scale factor a_i and δ_i as,

$$a_i = -\frac{\pi G \theta_i^2}{3\epsilon_i} \rho_i a_i^3 r_i^2, \quad (5.24)$$

$$\delta_i = \frac{3}{20} \theta_i^2, \quad (5.25)$$

The initial energy enclosed is given by,

$$\epsilon_i = -\frac{20\pi G}{9} \frac{\delta_i(r_i)}{a_i} \rho_i a_i^3 r_i. \quad (5.26)$$

Hence the linear density contrast in EdS universe can be parameterised as $\left(\delta_l = a \frac{\delta_i}{a_i}\right)$,

$$\delta_l = \frac{3}{20} [6(\theta - \sin(\theta))]^{2/3}. \quad (5.27)$$

A general expression for δ_l in terms of the non-linear density contrast δ is

$$\delta = \left(1 - \frac{\delta_l}{v}\right)^{-v} - 1, \quad (5.28)$$

with $v = \frac{21}{13}$ for the 3D case. [60]

5.4.3 Path Integral Formalism

Disentangling primordial non-Gaussianity from the late-time non-linear evolution induced non-Gaussianity is not trivial. An approach using the path integral formalism and saddle point approximation was discussed in [7, 20, 21, 22, 28, 63], and using the Large deviation principle in [60, 61, 64, 65, 66]. To arrive at the final late-time CGF, we follow the path integral formulation of integrating over all possible configurations of the linear density contrast δ_L . There are infinite possible ways/"paths" for a linear density field δ_L to evolve into a non-linear density field δ_{NL} (we add the subscript for clarity), and we sum over all the possibilities.

Before proceeding, let us briefly recall the path integral formalism in statistical field theory (SFT) as an analogy to move forward. Although there are many differences between what we discuss below and SFT, we can focus on the similarities, at least for better intuition.

For this case, we can consider a continuum field $\xi[\mathbf{x}]$, and this is the order parameter of the system. The generating functional/partition function then is

$$Z = \int \mathcal{D}\xi e^{-\beta \int d^d \mathbf{x} \mathcal{F}(\xi)}, \quad (5.29)$$

where, $\beta = \frac{1}{k_B T}$, and \mathcal{F} ³ is the free energy. The generating functional describes the integral over infinite configurations of the order parameter due to thermal fluctuations around the equilibrium configuration determined by the saddle point. Now, to map this analogy with the analysis of consideration, we first note that we are computing the generating functional (non-linear CGF) over all possible configurations of linear density contrast due to density fluctuations (leading to overdense and underdense regions), and we will use saddle point approximation to determine the evolution.

To evolve the linear density field to non-linear, as previously mentioned, we consider the spherical collapse formalism. This, unlike in the SFT or QFT framework, has non-local effects due to gravity.

We first begin by writing the expectation value of non-linear CGF as a functional integral over all possible configurations of δ_L as

$$e^{\phi_{NL}(\lambda)} \equiv \langle e^{\lambda \delta_{NL}} \rangle = \int \mathcal{D}\delta_L \mathcal{P}[\delta_L] e^{\lambda \delta_{NL}[\delta_L]}, \quad (5.30)$$

where $\mathcal{P}[\delta_L]$ is the probability density functional of the linear density contrast field δ_L and the non-linear density contrast δ_{NL} has been expressed as a functional of δ_L . $e^{\phi_{NL}(\lambda)}$ is the moment generating functional, and as mentioned in 5.2.1, we are going to write the probability functional in terms of the *action*.

To get the form of $\mathcal{P}[\delta_L]$, we consider the linear CGF contribution. Consider the evolution of the linear density field with 'external sources' \mathcal{J} that disturb the field,

$$\Phi[\mathcal{J}_L] = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n!} \int \prod_{i=1}^n d^3 x_i \mathcal{J}_L(\mathbf{x}_i) \xi_{L,n}(\mathbf{x}_1 \dots \mathbf{x}_n), \quad (5.31)$$

where $\Phi[\mathcal{J}_L]$ quantifies the contribution from the external sources' correlations at arbitrary locations, and it is the linear cumulant generating functional associated with $\mathcal{P}[\delta_L]$. $\xi_{L,n}(\mathbf{x}_1 \dots \mathbf{x}_n)$ is the equivalent of the connected Green's functions in QFT. We include the contribution of the CGF due to these sources' interactions, and the interaction with the density field. (Similar to self-interacting external sources & interaction with the field in the QFT perspective.) This makes sense since the probability functional is only dependent on the linear density contrast, we write down an *action* for δ_L which includes the source terms.

³The free energy can be written as the Legendre transform of internal energy as $F = E - TS$, where S is the entropy. Similar to this, we can write a transformation between the non-linear density contrast and the CGF, to be discussed in 5.5.2.

ϕ_{NL} then takes the form,

$$e^{\phi_{NL}(\lambda)} = \mathcal{N} \int \mathcal{D}\delta_L \mathcal{D}\mathcal{J}_L e^{\lambda\delta_{NL}[\delta_L] - i \int d^3\mathbf{x} \mathcal{J}_L(\mathbf{x}) \delta_L(\mathbf{x}) + \Phi[i\mathcal{J}_L]}, \quad (5.32)$$

\mathcal{N} is some normalisation constant that is irrelevant. For Gaussian initial conditions, $\Phi[\mathcal{J}_L]$ is described completely by the 2- point correlation function $\xi_{L,2}$, but in our case owing to the PNG, we consider the full n-point correlations.

We can solve the Eq 5.32 using the saddle-point method, since its a complex integral, or we can turn to Laplace method after a Wick rotation, and this would then turn out to be an optimization problem to minimize the action,

$$S_\lambda[\delta_L, \mathcal{J}_L] = -\lambda\delta_{NL}[\delta_L] + i\mathcal{J}_L\delta_L - \Phi[i\mathcal{J}_L]. \quad (5.33)$$

Here we have condensed the notations by writing $i\mathcal{J}_L\delta_L = i \int d^3\mathbf{x} \mathcal{J}_L(\mathbf{x}) \delta_L(\mathbf{x})$. The cumulant generating function of the late-time smoothed non-linear density field is then given by

$$\phi_{NL}(\lambda) \approx -S_\lambda[\delta_L^*, \mathcal{J}_L^*] - \frac{1}{2} \ln(\mathcal{A}), \quad (5.34)$$

where \mathcal{A} is the determinant of the Hessian matrix of the functional S , contributing in the second-order, lower than the action and will be ignored [7, 67].

5.4.4 Minimisation of Action

We need to minimise the action S_λ , which amounts to solving the minimisation equations,

$$\left. \frac{dS_\lambda}{d\delta_L(\mathbf{x})} \right|_{\delta_L^*, \mathcal{J}_L^*} = 0 = \left. \frac{dS_\lambda}{d\mathcal{J}_L(\mathbf{x})} \right|_{\delta_L^*, \mathcal{J}_L^*}. \quad (5.35)$$

Differentiating Eq 5.33, we get the form of the saddle-point configurations,

$$\lambda \left. \frac{d\delta_{NL}}{d\delta_L(\mathbf{x})} \right|_{\delta_L^*} = i\mathcal{J}_L^*(\mathbf{x}); \quad \left. \frac{d\Phi}{d\mathcal{J}_L(\mathbf{x})} \right|_{i\mathcal{J}_L^*} = \delta_L^*(\mathbf{x}). \quad (5.36)$$

To solve these optimisation problem, we define δ_{NL} in terms of δ_L using the spherical collapse model,

$$\mathcal{F}(\delta_{L,R_L}^*) = \delta_{NL}[\delta_L^*] = \left[\left(1 - \frac{\delta_L^*}{v} \right)^{-v} - 1 \right]; \quad v = \frac{21}{13}, \quad (5.37)$$

\mathcal{F} denotes the spherical collapse function from an initial radii R_L to a final radius R ($R_L = R(1 + \delta_R[\delta_L^*])^{1/3}$). We then substitute this in the first equation in 5.36, and simplify as follows

$$\left. \frac{d\delta_{NL}}{d\delta_L(\mathbf{x})} \right|_{\delta_L^*} = \mathcal{F}'(\delta_{L,R_L}^*) \left. \frac{d\delta_{L,R_L}}{d\delta_L(\mathbf{x})} \right|_{\delta_L^*}, \quad (5.38)$$

$$= \mathcal{F}'(\delta_{L,R_L}^*) \left(W_{R_L}(\mathbf{x}) + \left. \frac{d\delta_{L,R'}^*}{dR'} \right|_{R_L} \frac{R^3}{3R_L^2} \left. \frac{d\delta_{NL}}{d\delta_L(\mathbf{x})} \right|_{\delta_L^*} \right). \quad (5.39)$$

Here, $W_{R_L}(\mathbf{x})$ is the spherical top-hat window function that smoothes the linear density field with linear radii R_L , such that $\delta_{L,R_L} = \int d^3\mathbf{x}' W_{R_L}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}') \delta_L(\mathbf{x}')$. It was shown in [28], that the spherical collapse is the solution at the saddle point, and what we are computing is indeed the global minima of the action.

Now combining 5.38 and 5.36, we get,

$$\lambda \left. \frac{d\delta_{NL}}{d\delta_L(\mathbf{x})} \right|_{\delta_L^*} = i\mathcal{J}_L^*(\mathbf{x}) = \lambda \frac{\mathcal{F}'(\delta_{L,R_L}^*) W_{R_L}(\mathbf{x})}{1 - \mathcal{F}'(\delta_{L,R_L}^*) \left. \frac{d\delta_{L,R'}^*}{dR'} \right|_{R_L} \frac{R^3}{3R_L^2}}. \quad (5.40)$$

We can write the simplified expression of the form $i\mathcal{J}_L^*(\mathbf{x}) = \Gamma_\lambda[\delta_L^*] W_{R_L}(\mathbf{x})$. We substitute this back into the second equation in 5.36 and we get,

$$\begin{aligned} \left. \frac{d\Phi}{d\mathcal{J}_L(\mathbf{x})} \right|_{i\mathcal{J}_L^*} &= \delta_L^*(\mathbf{x}), \\ &= \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(n-1)!} \int \prod_{i=1}^{n-1} d^3x_i \mathcal{J}_L(\mathbf{x}_i) \xi_{L,n}(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2 \dots \mathbf{x}_n) \Big|_{i\mathcal{J}_L^*} = \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\Gamma_\lambda^{n-1}}{(n-1)!} \langle \delta_{L,R_L}^{n-1} \delta_L(\mathbf{x}) \rangle_c. \end{aligned} \quad (5.41)$$

We then smooth the initial linear density field with the linear radii and simplify further as

$$\delta_{L,R_L}^* = \left. \frac{d\varphi_{L,R_L}(j)}{dj} \right|_{A_\lambda=j} \quad (5.42)$$

φ is the linear CGF for the averaged linear density contrast over linear radii. Now,

$$\left. \frac{d\delta_{L,R'}^*}{dR'} \right|_{R'=R_L} = \frac{1}{A_\lambda} \left. \frac{d\varphi_{L,R_L}(j)}{dR'} \right|_{A_\lambda=j, R'=R_L}. \quad (5.43)$$

Equations 5.41, 5.42, 5.44 helps us minimise the action functional and we can write,

$$S_\lambda[\delta_L^*, \mathcal{J}_L^*] = -\lambda \mathcal{F}(\delta_{L,R_L}^*) + A_\lambda \delta_{L,R_L}^* - \varphi_{L,R_L}(A_\lambda). \quad (5.44)$$

We simplify the above equation by mapping to a 2D optimisation of a function

$$s(\delta, j) = -\lambda F(\delta) + j\delta - \varphi_{L,R(1+F(\delta))^{1/3}}, \quad (5.45)$$

and minimise the same, and we then arrive at the following conditions [7],

$$\left. \frac{\partial s_\lambda}{\partial j} \right|_{\delta=\delta^*, j=j^*} = 0 = \left. \frac{\partial s_\lambda}{\partial \delta} \right|_{\delta=\delta^*, j=j^*}, \quad (5.46)$$

leading to

$$j^* = \lambda F'(\delta) + \left. \frac{d\varphi_{L,R'}(j^*)}{dR'} \right|_{R'=R_L} \frac{R^3}{3R_L^2} F'(\delta), \quad (5.47)$$

and

$$\delta^* = \left. \frac{d\varphi_{L,R(1+F(\delta))^{1/3}}}{dj} \right|_{j=j^*}. \quad (5.48)$$

We solve the above equations (5.45, 5.47, 5.48) for our current case considering an entire map and not restricting to just an initial skewness configuration. We also perform the analysis considering just the skewness, and kurtosis contribution to the linear CGF.

5.4.5 Non-linear variance rescaling

The saddle-point approximation gives the cumulants of the non-linear density contrast at leading order in perturbation theory [7]. This can mean that the above approximation for the CGF might not yield the right variance of density fluctuations even in mildly non-linear regimes. To alleviate this issue, we consider the rescaled CGF, bringing back the S_n expansion. We then modify the final CGF re-written in terms of S_n and we get

$$\tilde{\varphi}_{NL,R}(\lambda) \equiv \sigma_R^2 \varphi\left(\frac{\lambda}{\sigma_R^2}\right). \quad (5.49)$$

Where σ_R^2 is the variance of a smoothed field over radius R . We can trace back and get Eq. 5.6 in terms of S_n . The reduced cumulants S_n are less sensitive to the non-linear evolution than the raw cumulants [5, 7]. Hence, we compute the linear variance and use it in the equation above, and invert back using the non-linear variance to get the final re-scaled CGF in the leading order contribution.

This is similar to the hierarchical rescaling by the linear variance for Gaussian initial conditions but here, we consider the non-linear variance to include the mild non-linear regime and non-Gaussian initial conditions. Remember that the saddle point formalism is only applicable when $-S_\lambda^* = 0$, and is a global minima. To to this, in case of Gaussian initial conditions, we rescale the CGF such that $\tilde{\varphi} = \sigma^2 \varphi\left(\frac{\lambda}{\sigma^2}\right)$, and then for quasi-linear approximation, we let $\sigma^2 \rightarrow 0$. Extrapolating to non-linear regimes, we consider the ratio of non-linear and linear variances,

$$\phi_{NL}(\lambda) = \frac{\sigma_{L,R}^2}{\sigma_{NL,R}^2} \varphi^{1.o}\left(\frac{\sigma_{NL,R}^2}{\sigma_{L,R}^2} \lambda\right). \quad (5.50)$$

To arrive at $\sigma_{NL,R}^2$, we first compute the non-linear matter power spectrum using the Halofit model [6]. I used Pylans code [68] to generate the non-linear power spectrum and I integrated with the spherical top-hat window function $\tilde{W}(k)$ to compute at the non-linear variance as,

$$\sigma_{L/NL,R}^2(z) = \int \frac{dk}{2\pi^2} P_{L/NL}(k, z) k^2 \tilde{W}_R^2(k). \quad (5.51)$$

Figure 5.1: Non-linear Power spectrum of the non-linear variance using the Halofit model [6], superposed with the linear power spectrum for comparison.

The ratio $\frac{\sigma_{NL,R}^2}{\sigma_{L,R}^2}$ for $R = 30 Mpc/h$ is 1.035. Non-linear variance increases and can be intuitively understood as follows: We can consider σ^2 as a clock, a time-dependent parameter that evolves during structure formation. For an initial density field in the region of interest with a certain radius, there is gravitational attraction pulling the particles closer towards each other, reducing the radius of the domain, hence increasing the variance. This happens until the overdensity passes through the critical $\delta_c = 1.686$ after which the structure virializes, as mentioned before.

We now proceed to discuss the results, particularly focusing on the non-linear late-time CGF and the cumulants for different initial setup conditions.

5.5 Results

5.5.1 Computing j^* and $\frac{d\varphi}{dR'}$

We begin with computing Eq. 5.47 and 5.48. We first set an array of δ^* (can be thought of initial linear density field δ_L), and compute $R_L, F(\delta), F'(\delta)$ using the spherical collapse framework. This is done by substituting δ^* in Eq 5.37. We can then use 5.48, and for the array of δ^* , invert the equation and get the second saddle point configuration j^* .

We then use this array to compute λ after computing $\frac{d\varphi}{dR'}$ for every R_L in Eq 5.47. Finally, with this, we compute the final non-linear CGF once we find the function $s_\lambda(\delta^*, j^*)$ and perform the appropriate rescaling of variance. Starting with the expression for CGF,

$$e^{\phi_{NL}} \equiv \langle e^{\delta_{RL} \lambda} \rangle, \quad (5.52)$$

$$\implies \phi_{RL} = \ln(\langle e^{\delta_{RL} \lambda} \rangle), \quad (5.53)$$

then the linear CGF as a function of 'j' is,

$$\implies \varphi'_{R_L, j} = \frac{\langle \delta_{R_L} e^{\delta_{R_L} j} \rangle}{\langle e^{\delta_{R_L} j} \rangle} \quad (5.54)$$

The minima of φ'_{R_L, j^*} is stored as an array of δ^* (using 5.43) given by,

$$\boxed{\delta_i^* - \frac{\langle \delta_{R_L i} e^{\delta_{R_L i} j_i^*} \rangle}{\langle e^{\delta_{R_L i} j_i^*} \rangle} = 0} \quad (5.55)$$

δ_{R_L} is our δ_m map from the Axion U(1) inflation after the appropriate transfer function, smoothed over an array of linear radii R_L . Now we are left to compute $\frac{d\varphi_{L,R}(j)}{dR}$. We once again revert to the expressions for the CGF,

$$\varphi_{L,R}(j) = \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \langle \delta_{L,R}^n \rangle \frac{j^n}{n!}, \quad (5.56)$$

$$\implies e^{\phi_{L,R}(j)} = \langle e^{j\delta_{L,R}} \rangle, \quad (5.57)$$

$$\implies \varphi_{L,R}(j) = \ln \langle e^{j \int d^3x W_R(\mathbf{x}-\mathbf{x}') \delta_L(\mathbf{x}')} \rangle. \quad (5.58)$$

Where $W_R(x)$ is a spherical top-hat window function over the smoothing radius R, given by,

$$W_R(x) = \frac{3}{4\pi R^3} \Theta(R - |\mathbf{x}|) \quad (5.59)$$

So the derivative with respect to R' is

$$\left. \frac{d\varphi_{L,R}(j)}{dR'} \right|_{R'=R_L} = \frac{\langle j \left. \frac{d\delta_{L,R}}{dR'} \right|_{R'=R_L} e^{j \int d^3x W_R(\mathbf{x}-\mathbf{x}') \delta_L(\mathbf{x}')} \rangle}{\langle e^{j \int d^3x W_R(\mathbf{x}-\mathbf{x}') \delta_L(\mathbf{x}')} \rangle}, \quad (5.60)$$

$$\left. \frac{d\delta_{L,R}}{dR'} \right|_{R'=R_L} = \int d^3x \left. \frac{dW_R(\mathbf{x}-\mathbf{x}')}{dR'} \right|_{R'=R_L} \delta_L(\mathbf{x}'). \quad (5.61)$$

Differentiating the window function with respect to the radius is the only computation here and is trivial,

$$\tilde{W}_R(x) \equiv \frac{dW_R(x)}{dR'} = -\frac{9}{4\pi R^4} \Theta(R - |\mathbf{x}|) + D \cdot \Theta. \quad (5.62)$$

$D \cdot \Theta$ refers to differential terms of the Heaviside function, which goes to zero as it results in a delta-dirac function not evaluated at 0. Hence this 'new' window function \tilde{W}_R is used to smooth the linear density field for every R_L , and we can then compute $\frac{d\varphi}{dR'}$. Now that we have the setup to compute j^* and $\varphi'_{R'}$, we can compute λ from Eq. 5.47, and then arrive at the late-time non-linear CGF via

$$\phi_{NL}(\lambda) = \lambda F(\delta) - j\delta + \varphi_{L,R(1+F(\delta))^{1/3}}(j), \quad (5.63)$$

evaluated at $j = j^*$, $\delta = \delta^*$, and finally, we perform the non-linear variance re-scaling.

We conduct the analysis for the full map, and considering just skewness, and kurtosis contribution in the initial CGF. We consider a $V = 100(GPc/h)^3$ box volume, roughly of the order of comoving length 4.634 Gpc/h. We smooth the δ_m for the radius $R = 30$ Mpc/h. To begin with we modify the initial ζ .

We consider a spectator field along with the U(1) Axion inflation as a prototype to instill a mild non-Gaussianity in the initial setup. This is in-line with $\delta\phi = \delta\phi_{vac} + \delta\phi_{inv\ decay}$ mentioned earlier during the discussion about Axion inflation. Here, loosely speaking, the coefficient 'a' dictates the contribution to non-Gaussianity from the sourced terms.

$$\zeta_{NG} = \zeta_G + a\zeta_{U(1)}, \quad (5.64)$$

ζ_G is the curvature perturbation due to a single scalar field inflaton. We now normalise the variance of ζ_{NG} and that of ζ_G so that the power spectrum of the two align, and the higher order correlations' impact is better analysed. We performed the analysis for different coefficients, for both $a > 0$; $a < 0$. We cannot increase 'a' arbitrarily without affecting the power spectrum, hence there is a limiting value of $a = 0.5$.

We first compute the linear CGF for reference and a quick check of correctness. We smooth the matter density field δ_{m_L} for the required radius, and then compute $\phi_L(\lambda) = \ln \langle e^{\lambda\delta_{m_L}} \rangle$ for lambda values $\lambda_L \in (-2/\sigma_L, 2/\sigma_L)$ for the standard deviation of the smoothed linear field. Figure 5.2(b) shows the plots of both linear and non-linear CGF, the linear CGF is close to Gaussian with a slight extended tail end region towards the left, this is due to the choice of the sign in front of the coefficient of 'a' in initial ζ_{NG} . We then perform the entire analysis and get the non-linear CGF with a clear non-Gaussian effect imprinted and with an extended tail towards the right, this nature is reversed if we change the sign of 'a'.

Next question that might arise is on the range of δ^* array to be used, since this directly affects j^* and that in turn is the major contribution to λ . (All other terms in the computation of λ are of $\mathcal{O}(1)$) Before we delve into the results of non-linear CGFs of non-Gaussian vs Gaussian field, we take a short detour to discuss critical points of λ and a brief introduction to large deviation theory.

5.5.2 Large Deviation Theory and LSS

Large deviation theory (LDT) is useful in analysing the tail end of the PDF, as opposed to Central limit theorem that dictates the form of the distribution close to the mean. It is particularly important in studying the rare-events, and posits an exponential decay of the tail region wherein the PDF $\mathcal{P}_L(\delta_L) \sim e^{-|\delta_L|}$, instead of the usual Gaussian form. LDT in the large-scale structure studies has mainly been used to compute the one-point statistics of the smoothed density field [60, 61]. It has also been extended to the joint distribution between densities measured at some distance [69], and recently to the early-universe [70]. LDT, traditionally has been applied and *is* the mathematical framework underpinning statistical mechanics [71]. In case of LSS and one-point PDF, we first begin

Figure 5.2: To the left: Power spectrum of $\delta_{m_{NG}}$ and δ_{m_G} for coefficient $a = 0.1$ and comoving length of the box $L = 4634 \text{ Mpc}/h$ using Pylans with variance $\sigma^2 = 0.298$. To the right: Non-linear vs Linear CGF for the non-Gaussian initial condition and for $a = 0.12$ and $\delta^* \in (-0.1, 0.1)$.

with considering a set of random variables ρ^ϵ which are i.i.d, and each having a PDF $\mathcal{P}_\epsilon(\rho^\epsilon)$, and they are said to satisfy the large-deviation statistics if the limit

$$\Psi_{\rho^\epsilon}(\rho^\epsilon) = -\lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \epsilon [\log(\mathcal{P}_\epsilon(\rho^\epsilon))], \quad (5.65)$$

exists, ϵ is the driving parameter and Ψ is the rate-function that describes the exponential decay of the PDF. The driving parameter ϵ is a random variable with respect to an evolution, say with respect to time. In the case of LSS, it can describe the variance of a smoothed matter density field (radius R) and can act as a clock from initial linear field to late-time evolved non-linear field. ($\epsilon \sim \sigma_R^2$).

In LDT framework, the scaled CGF (SCGF) is given through the Varadhan's theorem using the Legendre-Fenchel transform.⁴

$$\varphi_\rho(\lambda) = \sup_\rho \{\lambda\rho - \Psi_\rho(\rho)\}. \quad (5.66)$$

Imposing Ψ_ρ to be convex then leads to a Legendre transform, and in that case,

$$\varphi_\rho(\lambda) = \lambda\rho - \Psi_\rho(\rho), \quad (5.67)$$

then λ is given by the usual stationary condition,

$$\lambda = \frac{\partial \Psi_\rho(\rho)}{\partial \rho}. \quad (5.68)$$

⁴A generalisation of legendre transform to include non-convex and non-differentiable functions as well given by $f^*(k) = \sup_{x \in \mathbb{R}} \{kx - f(x)\}$, with weaker restrictions on the function [72].

When the rate function ceases to be convex, $\lambda = \lambda_c$ reaches the critical point, and in that case the MGF is no longer well-defined. At this point $\Psi''_{\rho_c} = 0$ and the critical density $\rho = \rho_c$. One more consequence of LDT is the contraction principle in which there exists a mapping between $\rho \rightarrow \tau$ in line with $\delta \rightarrow F(\delta)(\delta_{NL})$, and knowing the rate-function of one, we can invert map to find the rate function of the other. For example, the rate function $\Psi_\rho(\rho)$ can be determined if we know the rate function of τ , and we do know such a function for specific geometries - spherically symmetric or cylindrical, etc.

Here we consider a spherically symmetric geometry with a spherical top-hat window function, and a definitive relationship $F(\delta)$ that helps us map ' ρ ' to ' τ '. This is called the contraction principle because F can be many-to-one, in which case we are contracting information about the rate function of one random variable down to the other [60, 64, 73]. In physical terms, this states that an improbable fluctuation of ρ is brought about by the most probable of all improbable fluctuations of τ .⁵ Moreover, we can map from ρ to δ via $\Psi_\delta(\delta) = \Psi_\rho(\rho(\delta))$. We can then use the usual re-scaling of variance and compute S_n , and finally get the CGF using the legendre transform shown above. Re-scaling by the non-linear variance allows access to the full one-point statistics of the non-linear density field [7]. The SCGF given by the LDT is the asymptotic form taken by the cumulants of the field in the regime where $\sigma_R^2 \rightarrow 0$. But how do we use this information to compute the critical points of λ , particularly for our case?

To do that, we first note the similarity between Eq. 5.63 and 5.66, one is by Saddle-point approximation and Path integral formalism, and the other using LDT. Remember that the saddle-point approximation breaks down when the function ceases to be convex. If we map $\rho \rightarrow F(\delta)$ and $j\delta - \varphi_{L,R}(1+F(\delta))^{1/3} \rightarrow \Psi_\rho(\rho)$, then we can use Eq. 5.68 to arrive at the critical lambda after finding $\Psi''_{\rho_c} = 0$ the critical density values, and finding the corresponding critical lambda using $\Psi'_{\rho_c} = \lambda_c$.

This can be, practically speaking, a bit tricky to do on Python. For the following reason: It is possible for the code to attach a 'psuedo-convexity envelope' even when the convexity condition is no longer valid, since the code just performs the calculation without considering any assumptions. One can see such an artifact in the CGF plot if one has provided initial δ^* values just over the critical value. Even in this case, there are ways to compute the critical point. We continue with the mapping and compute the derivatives to analyse the breakdown of convexity. Figure 5.4 shows one way to compute the critical point. It is by using the mapping from LDT to saddle-point as shown, but this is purely for convenience, the physical interpretation needs to be excluded. Conceptually speaking, the rate function is computed using the initial mapping from $\rho \rightarrow \tau$, and then using a specific geometric smoothing, one computes the initial CGF in terms of $\langle \delta^n \rangle$, Legendre transforms to arrive at the initial rate-function. And subsequently use the contraction

⁵The most likely dynamics amongst all possible mappings between the initial and final density field is the one respecting a particular kind of symmetry [20]. This is a result of the contraction principle in the context of large deviation theory as explained in [66], and this is the meaning of the: amongst all unlikely events (the tail of the PDF) the least unlikely one (i.e. the spherical collapse solution) dominates [60].

Figure 5.3: To the left: CGF of non-Gaussian and Gaussian initial conditions with the critical point $\lambda_c \approx 18.86$. The code then continues beyond it even though theoretically there should be a branch cut. To the right: CGF plot from Cosmumentum [7] showing the branch cut after crossing λ_c , in Python if the code passes close (to a numerical accuracy) or exactly through λ_c , a branch cut is seen, else, the code assumes convexity throughout and continues the computation.

Figure 5.4: To the left: The second derivative of Ψ to determine the critical density point, the rise in the curve cuts the $\Psi = 0$ at $\delta = \delta_c$, and we substitute this for $F(\delta)$ in our computation. To the right: The first derivative plot, for the corresponding δ_c (δ_{NLc}), we can compute the critical lambda value or at least close to it and compute the δ^* values correspondingly.

principle [64, 66]. Here, we only loosely map to extract information about λ_c , defining a function ' Ψ ' equivalent to the rate-function provides us a way to identify the critical overdensity and δ_{NL} . Moreover, intuitively, writing down the rate function, and the Legendre transform motivates us to revert back to the statistical field theoretic picture. Let us examine the similarities and differences again. Equation 5.67 is similar to $F = U - TS$ in the usual statistical/thermodynamics framework, and past the critical point during phase transition, F ceases to exist. Similarly, we can associate $\beta = \frac{1}{k_B T}$ to λ , and the critical point, mathematically symbolises a "phase transition" and our results cannot be trusted. One should also keep in mind, the difference in the mapping. The critical point is a mathematical artifact, physically speaking, we work well within the limit $\delta_L < 1$, after which the perturbative method breaks down, and it is not a quasi-linear regime anymore. This also translates to $\sigma^2 \rightarrow 0$. Moreover, there is no small scale cutoff due to shell-crossing, and we work in regimes in which the leading order perturbation theory is valid.

5.5.3 CGF and Moments

Once we compute the critical lambda points, we can initialise the code in such a way that we avoid λ_c , hence with a reasonable δ^* array. We can then perform the analysis and arrive at the final CGF after appropriate rescaling, shown in Fig. 5.5. Further, we aim to compute the cumulants and estimate the ratio of the cumulants with primordial non-Gaussian conditions and with the Gaussian ICs. (With the spectator field and just a simple scalar field.)

To do that, we first introduce another parameter Λ , to rescale δ^* . The reason is that the CGF is plotted on a grid with a corresponding λ . In order to extract individual cumulants from that, one can simply fit a polynomial of finite degree in λ to the CGF $\phi_R(\lambda)$. This is unstable due to the difference in the number of positive values mapped from $\lambda(\delta^*) \rightarrow \delta^*$ compared to the negative values. This is evident from the CGF plot, there is an extended leg towards the right compared to left [7].

Cumulants and Bell polynomials

To extract the individual moments, we first introduce

$$\Lambda(\delta^*) = \frac{\delta^*}{\langle (\delta_{L,R_L(\delta^*)})^2 \rangle_c}. \quad (5.69)$$

We then fit a polynomial of finite order 'N' in Λ to both $\lambda(\Lambda)$ and $\phi_{NL}(\lambda(\Lambda))$. We compute the $N \times N$ Bell-Jabotinsky matrices [7] as

$$(B^{\lambda|\Lambda})_{k,l} = \frac{1}{k!} \left. \frac{d^k \lambda^l}{d\Lambda^k} \right|_{\Lambda=0}; \quad (B^{\phi|\Lambda})_{k,l} = \frac{1}{k!} \left. \frac{d^k \phi^l}{d\Lambda^k} \right|_{\Lambda=0}. \quad (5.70)$$

We finally arrive at the Bell-Jabotinsky matrices of ϕ with respect to λ as

$$\mathbf{B}^{\phi|\Lambda} = \mathbf{B}^{\phi|\Lambda} \cdot (\mathbf{B}^{\lambda|\Lambda})^{-1}. \quad (5.71)$$

Figure 5.5: CGF of non-Gaussian and Gaussian field with coefficient $a = 0.12$ and $\delta^* \in (-0.1, 0.11)$.

We are fitting a finite order polynomial to a CGF which in principle is infinite, hence, the results are subjected to numerical errors, dependent on the redshift and smoothing scale, and need to be interpreted appropriately.

We first begin by plotting for $a=0.1$, and for $\delta_L \in (-0.1, 0.11)$, and we notice in Fig 5.6 that the initial CGF with just the skewness $\varphi_{L,R}(j) = \frac{\langle \delta_{L,R}^2 \rangle^c}{2!} j^2 + \frac{\langle \delta_{L,R}^3 \rangle^c}{3!} j^3$ grows consistently. For the initial CGF with kurtosis and the entire box, there is a strong peak at $n=3$, and a drop till $n=4$, and grows again, this behavior is discussed below. We also plot the cumulants of just the PNG contribution and we notice that the cumulants from the entire box ICs grows and overtakes the others. This growth, particularly at higher moments is important and is a signature of the inflationary model we consider. But, an obvious question that arises is why is it that there is a dip in the cumulants ratio at $n=3$ for kurtosis and higher order moments ICs? Before we attempt to answer that, whenever there is a higher moments contribution in the analysis, the effect of spherical collapse there should be to replace $F(\delta)$ by the inverse spherical collapse, so $F^{-1}(\delta) = \delta^*[\delta_{NL}]$, and we can proceed with the usual mapping of scales, $R_L = R (1 + \delta_{NL})^{1/3}$. What happens if we perform the usual spherical collapse? The reduced cumulant $\epsilon_3^2 = \frac{\kappa_3^2}{\sigma^2}$ if large could contribute to the increasing ratio for $n=4$, and then in the presence of initial kurtosis, ϵ_4 's presence can cancel this contribution to an extent, leading to a dip at $n=3$. (This can be understood as interplay between f_{NL} and g_{NL} when f_{NL}^2 is $\approx g_{NL}$ [60])

For this analysis, we first begin by assuming an initial δ_{NL} , we invert Equation 5.28 to get

$$\delta^* = v[1 - (1 + \delta_{NL})^{-1/v}]. \quad (5.72)$$

We then compute R_L for various δ_{NL} and subsequently compute j^* and λ as usual. And the rest of the analysis follows the same steps. We further compute the non-linear CGF contribution to the fifth cumulant to the initial CGF. What difference would the full box showcase compared to the third, fourth or fifth cumulant alone is the question in

(a) Moments plot of $\frac{(\delta^n)_{c, PNG}}{(\delta^n)_{c, G}}$ for Skewness, Kurtosis, and considering the whole box.

(b) Moments plot for just the PNG contribution for Skewness, Kurtosis, and the whole box.

Figure 5.6: To the left: The cumulants growth for various initial CGF. There is a continued growth of the moments for skewness but at $n=3$, the cumulants of the entire map ICs and kurtosis drops, and they grow again after $n=4$ ($n=2$ is the variance here) To the right: The growth of just the PNG contribution, there is again a peak for kurtosis but the entire box eventually overtakes the skewness and kurtosis past $n=5$, and that is important for the analysis.

Figure 5.7: To the left: The cumulants growth for various initial CGF after the inverse SC including the fifth cumulant to the initial CGF. We notice that there is a smaller dip in the value for the whole box at $n=4$, compared to the right which is the usual spherical collapse. This is fitted for 13th degree polynomial for $a = 0.1$.

hand. We notice a reduction in the drop of the cumulants value for the whole box from $n=3$ to $n=4$, and for kurtosis and the fifth cumulant at $n=3$, and this is attributed to the reduction in the initial δ_L due to inverse spherical collapse. More importantly, the reason the behavior of the full box different from the rest might mean that the interplay between ϵ 's is not restricted to just ϵ_3, ϵ_4 but can be extrapolated to higher rescaled cumulants effects' too. The interplay of higher order cumulants and their interaction defines the behaviour of the full box compared to the kurtosis only or the fifth moment only.

We note from Figure 5.7, introducing an initial fifth moment to the linear CGF alters the analysis very little, there is a slight reduction compared to kurtosis at $n=5$. Further to determine why there is no linear growth of cumulants as expected for the Axion inflationary model, we return to analysing the linear CGF and its moments. The cumulants for Gaussian map are non-existent after $n=2$. (The spectator field *does not* follow the same pattern in the growth of cumulants, in other words $\kappa_5 > \kappa_4 > \kappa_3$ is not true.) We note from Figure 5.9(a), the linear map for the full box has the same behavior, with a peak at $n=3$. An interesting point that is attributed to non-linear evolution at play is from $n=4$ to $n=5$, the growth is evident in the non-linear CGF's cumulants. This growth is also observed for other initial CGF setups, as seen in Fig. 5.7. This can be due to the fact that higher order cumulants can affect the lower order ones, as explained in terms of ϵ 's earlier.

We can further compare the results by computing the cumulants growth for an initial

Figure 5.8: Moments plot of $\frac{\langle \delta^n \rangle_{c, PNG}}{\langle \delta^n \rangle_{c, G}}$ for Skewness for different degrees of polynomial as a consistency check using our analysis for inverse spherical collapse and to the right using Cosmomentum for same δ^* and R .

Figure 5.9: To the left: The cumulants growth from the linear CGF considering the entire map. To the right: The same growth post the spherical collapse formalism from the non-linear CGF and this explains the drop at $n=3$ for the entire map, the linear CGF behaves the same way as a result of the initial ζ_{NG} formulation.

Figure 5.10: Moments plot of $\frac{\langle \delta^n \rangle_{c, PNG}}{\langle \delta^n \rangle_{c, G}}$ for skewness, and the whole box at a different 'a'.

skewness only CGF and with the same δ^* and R using the Cosmumentum code [7]. Here, we do not consider the spectator field but just a primordial no-Gaussian contribution with a particular f_{NL} and an initial skewness. We note in Figure 5.8 the differences in the cumulants plot. If we follow the spherical collapse formalism, the moments' growth from $n=3$ to $n=4$ is suppressed than $n=4$ to $n=5$, while the Cosmumentum code shows no such variation, it is more or less uniform and linear. This is owing to the linear CGF behavior. In general, we can argue that the reduction in the cumulants value at $n=3$ is the least for skewness initial configuration, and is the closest to the full box. In our work, we attempted to generalise the Cosmumentum code, and computed the effects of higher order cumulants, and we observe that their effects are important in understanding the late-time non-Gaussianity effects induced primordially.

Now, it is important to specify some caveats. If the coefficient 'a' has a really low value, it is difficult to distinguish the contribution of the actual non-Gaussianity to noise, for instance there are non-zero higher order cumulants even for Gaussian initial conditions. It is then possible for both ζ_{NG} and the Gaussian map to have the same order of cumulants, but the higher order cumulants for Gaussian map represents the noise and is due to numerical errors induced. To distinguish, we can increase the value of the coefficient and note the variation of the cumulants for both linear and non-linear analysis. The initial coefficient 'a' has a sensitive dependence on the cumulants, for $a = 0.35$, with a mild modification to the power spectrum, we plot the cumulants growth in Fig 5.10. We notice a peak at $n=4$ for the linear and the same behavior is observed after the non-linear analysis as well.

We once again observe that the full box initial CGF resembles the closest to the linear CGF, as opposed to the skewness only initial setup. This is not surprising, the skewness contribution from the PNG is only till $n=3$, for $n > 3$, non-linear evolution of structure formation induces the growth. While the same evolution induces growth for the full box too, we do not see the difference due to the stronger PNG dependence on the same.

We have computed the growth of cumulants of an initial spectator field with an Axion inflationary model that sources non-Gaussianity. The full box initial configuration is clearly different from 'skewness' only analysis due to the way late-time non-Gaussianity affects the two. We also observe the same when we increase the coefficient in-turn reducing the noise level, and aiming to detect only the pure non-Gaussian contributions.

Chapter 6

Conclusion and Future Work

6.1 Discussion

Disentangling primordial non-Gaussian contribution from the late-time gravity induced non-Gaussianity is one of the many unsolved problems in LSS Cosmology. First, to analyse non-Gaussian signatures, one can either compute the n-point correlation functions or consider the global non-perturbative formalism of analysing the PDF. Within this PDF framework, there are two main ways to approach the problem of disentangling PNG from LNG: one is by Path integral formalism and Saddle-point approximation [7, 28, 21, 22, 20], and the other by Large deviation theory (LDT) [60, 61, 69, 73, 66, 64]. The attempts in doing so, so far, have been restricted to only considering the skewness [7] (3-point function or the Bispectrum) or the kurtosis [60] in the initial PNG distribution.

In this thesis, we built a new framework to investigate the effect of higher order cumulants sourced due to primordial non-Gaussianity during the late-time evolution of the universe until redshift $z = 1.0$. We considered a spectator field of the form $\zeta_{NG} = \zeta_G + a\zeta_{U(1)}$ as a prototype, where $U(1)$ is the non-Gaussian component attributed to the Axion inflationary model. To generate the ζ_{NG} map, we implemented Lattice simulations developed by [24]. We considered a comoving length of the box $L = 4634 \text{ Mpc}/h$, and $256 \times 256 \times 256$ elements along each axis. We computed the same for Gaussian initial conditions as well, considering the usual scalar field inflaton. We aimed to analyse the PNG contribution from higher order cumulants considering the entire map of ζ_{NG} .

We first analysed the non-Gaussian signatures of $U(1)$ Axion inflation and it obeys $\kappa_5 > \kappa_4 > \kappa_3$. We plotted the 3D map of ζ and the PDF histogram showing an extended tail at the right. We then obtained the linear prediction δ_m of matter overdensity (for ζ_{NG}) using the Einstein-Boltzmann equations solver CLASS, after applying transfer functions. Before delving into the analysis to arrive at the CGF, it was important to normalise the variance between the two maps for a specific value of 'a' to make sure there is no large deviation from the power spectrum. This is important to clearly analyse the effect of higher

order cumulants. We normalised the variance at two different steps: 1 - After the transfer functions, for the δ_m map for both non-Gaussian and Gaussian initial conditions; 2 - We normalise the variance after linear radii R_L smoothing for both the fields. In our work, we considered the comoving radius $R = 30 \text{ MPc/h}$.

We then computed the linear and non-linear late-time Cumulant generating function (CGF) using the path integral formalism and implementing spherical collapse formalism to induce the late-time non-linearity due to gravity [7]. We finally performed the necessary non-linear variance re-scaling for the latter. This rescaling was necessary for obtaining the right variance, and considering that we worked in the mild non-linear regime. We also applied the formalism of LDT to map between the rate function and the linear CGF contribution to obtain the critical points of λ , beyond which the saddle-point approximation is not valid, and convexity of the CGF breaks-down.

Once we obtained the late-time non-linear CGF, we computed the growth of the cumulants for the non-Gaussian and the Gaussian case using Bell polynomials and analysed the results of the ratio of the two for different initial CGF conditions: We considered the entire map that contains all the cumulants, and with just the initial skewness (IS), initial kurtosis (IK), and the fifth power (FP). We initially noted that IS grew constantly till $n=5$, with a slight dip at $n=3$ (there is a mild suppression since linear CGF is only till $n=3$, and post that is from the non-linear evolution part), while the entire map (full box), IK and FP dropped from $n=3$ to $n=4$ and then grew again from $n=4$. This then motivated us to understand the interplay between the reduced cumulants ϵ_4 and ϵ_3 , and we modified the analysis by considering the inverse spherical collapse, and we then noticed a very mild reduction in the suppression for the full box at $n=4$ owing to a reduced initial δ^* .

We further performed the analysis considering FP, and noted very little difference. We noticed the full box's contribution to the cumulants at $n=3$ is higher than that of fifth power only IC but lower than kurtosis, while the skewness shows very little suppression. We also noted that for the PNG only contribution, the full box contribution eventually overtook the rest. We further compared our results with that of the Cosmofit code for the same initial conditions and noticed an enhancement for our setup, and the skewness plot from our analysis was not a continuous linear growth.

Then the shape of the cumulants' plot motivated us to plot the κ 's of the non-Gaussian field before the non-linear evolution. We noticed that the linear cumulants are of the form $\kappa_4 > \kappa_5 > \kappa_3$, translating to the behaviour of the ratio in the late-time. This result was still susceptible to noise in the simulation, hence we increased the value of the coefficient 'a' and performed the analysis to extract maximum possible PNG contribution as opposed to noise, and we noted the same behaviour in the late-time CGF. We plotted it for different degrees of the polynomial fit for both skewness only and the full box. The non-linear evolution of PNG affects skewness more than the full box, and this is not surprising owing to the value of the coefficient 'a', in turn having an enhanced PNG contribution to the full box. Importantly, we observed that there is an interplay between higher order cumulants due to gravity induced non-Gaussianity, and it affects different initial configurations differently,

and this further implies, there is a possibility of extracting information beyond the skewness or kurtosis.

6.2 Future Work

This thesis marks the beginning of the direction towards understanding the higher order cumulants' effect due to primordial non-Gaussianity using the full late-time PDF approach. We considered the U(1) Axion inflationary model as the prototype owing to the interesting growth of its higher order cumulants. In the future, we aim to make the results robust by considering different initial setup conditions for the Axion inflation, and without considering the spectator field. We then aim to understand the physical reason and the higher order cumulants' interplay between skewness only and the full box initial setup due to the gravity-induced non-Gaussianity.

We further intend to improve the accuracy of the results by considering $512 \times 512 \times 512$ points along each axis for the lattice simulation, and understand the effect of inverse spherical collapse on the different initial CGF setup, reducing the noise with the better resolution. This would help us compute till order the cumulant of $n=6$. Once we realise and understand the importance of higher order cumulants during the late-time evolution of the universe, we aim to constrain the inflationary parameter ξ using the full late-time PDF.

The framework built can be generalised to an arbitrary inflationary model which generates a significant amount of primordial non-Gaussianity. The PNG signatures disentangled after structure formation can complement, and the results will be comparable to the N-Body simulations of LSS. We would further like to compare our results with the Quijote simulations as a test of robustness.

Appendix A

Computing $\frac{d\phi}{dR'}$ and j^* for Skewness and Kurtosis

We begin by assuming an array of δ^* as usual and aim to compute j^* first. The initial CGF for the skewness is

$$\varphi_{R_L}(j) = \frac{\langle \delta_{R_L}^2 \rangle_c}{2!} j^2 + \frac{\langle \delta_{R_L}^3 \rangle_c}{3!} j^3 \quad (\text{A.1})$$

And equation $\left. \frac{d\varphi_{R_L}(j)}{dj} \right|_{j=j^*} = \delta^*$, we get a quadratic equation

$$\frac{\langle \delta_{R_L}^3 \rangle_c}{2} j^{*2} + \langle \delta_{R_L}^3 \rangle_c j^* - \delta^* = 0 = j^{*2} + 2 \frac{\langle \delta_{R_L}^2 \rangle_c}{\langle \delta_{R_L}^3 \rangle_c} j^* - \frac{2}{\langle \delta_{R_L}^3 \rangle_c} \delta^* = 0 \quad (\text{A.2})$$

Solving Eq. A.2, we arrive at an array of j^* , and now to compute $\frac{d\phi}{dR'}$, we differentiate A.1 with respect to R' and we get

$$\left. \frac{d\varphi_{R_L}(j)}{dR'} \right|_{R'=R_L} = \frac{\langle \delta_{R_L} \frac{d\delta_{R_L}}{dR'} \Big|_{R'=R_L} \rangle_c}{2!} j^2 + \frac{\langle \delta_{R_L}^2 \frac{d\delta_{R_L}}{dR'} \Big|_{R'=R_L} \rangle_c}{3!} j^3 \quad (\text{A.3})$$

$\frac{d\delta_{R_L}}{dR'}$ can be evaluated as mentioned before by differentiating the Window function and arriving at a new 'Window function' and smoothing R_{L_s} over it.

We can now perform the same analysis including kurtosis in the initial CGF.

$$\varphi_{R_L}(j) = \frac{\langle \delta_{R_L}^2 \rangle_c}{2!} j^{*2} + \frac{\langle \delta_{R_L}^3 \rangle_c}{3!} j^{*3} + \frac{\langle \delta_{R_L}^4 \rangle_c}{4!} j^{*4} \quad (\text{A.4})$$

After substituting equation $\left. \frac{d\varphi_{R_L}(j)}{dj} \right|_{j=j^*} = \delta^*$, we get a cubic equation of the form

$$\frac{\langle \delta_{R_L}^4 \rangle_c}{6} j^{*3} + \frac{\langle \delta_{R_L}^3 \rangle_c}{2} j^{*2} + \langle \delta_{R_L}^2 \rangle_c j^* - \delta^* = 0 = j^{*3} + 6 \frac{\langle \delta_{R_L}^3 \rangle_c}{\langle \delta_{R_L}^4 \rangle_c} j^{*2} + 2 \frac{\langle \delta_{R_L}^2 \rangle_c}{\langle \delta_{R_L}^4 \rangle_c} j^* - \frac{6}{\langle \delta_{R_L}^4 \rangle_c} \delta^* = 0 \quad (\text{A.5})$$

Solving Eq. A.5, we arrive at an array of j^* , and now to compute $\frac{d\phi}{dR'}$, we differentiate A.4 with respect to R' and we get

$$\left. \frac{d\varphi_{R_L}(j)}{dR'} \right|_{R'=R_L} = \frac{\langle \delta_{R_L} \frac{d\delta_{R_L}}{dR'} \Big|_{R'=R_L} \rangle_c}{2!} j^{*2} + \frac{\langle \delta_{R_L}^2 \frac{d\delta_{R_L}}{dR'} \Big|_{R'=R_L} \rangle_c}{3!} j^{*3} + \frac{\langle \delta_{R_L}^3 \frac{d\delta_{R_L}}{dR'} \Big|_{R'=R_L} \rangle_c}{4!} j^{*4} \quad (\text{A.6})$$

Finally, we compute λ and $-s_\lambda(\delta^*, j^*)$ and the CGF, and get the non-linear CGF by variance re-scaling.

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